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EXPLORING THE X-RAY UNIVERSE IN THE MICROCALORIMETER ERA

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Digital Object Identifier: <https://doi.org/10.13023/etd.2021.396>

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EXPLORING THE X-RAY UNIVERSE IN THE MICROCALORIMETER ERA

DISSERTATION

A dissertation submitted in partial
fulfillment of the requirements for
the degree of Doctor of Philosophy
in the College of Arts and Sciences
at the University of Kentucky

By
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Lexington, Kentucky

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2021

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ABSTRACT OF DISSERTATION

EXPLORING THE X-RAY UNIVERSE IN THE MICROCALORIMETER ERA

Next-generation microcalorimeter missions like *XRISM* and *Athena* will revolutionize X-ray spectroscopy by offering a plethora of high-resolution X-ray spectra. Interpreting these observations requires a complete understanding of how matter interacts with light through such microphysical processes as absorption and excitation. I developed a framework describing the atomic processes for both collisionally-ionized and photoionized plasmas over a wide range of column densities. Through various line-intensity and line-ratio spectral diagnostics, I established four asymptotic limits; Cases A, B, C, and D. These apply to the formation of lines in H- and He-like systems. This is the first work describing these limits in the X-ray regime. I discussed line optical depth effects in H- and He-like iron with applications to the *Hitomi* observations of hot gas in the Perseus cluster of galaxies. I introduced a novel method of measuring column density using the Case A to B (optically thin to thick) transition by comparing the observed spectra by *Hitomi* with spectra simulated with the spectral synthesis code `CLOUDY`. I explored the effects of Li-like iron on the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ line intensities through Resonant Auger Destruction (RAD) and line broadening effects by electron scattering. These methods are now in place and will be available to the community by the launch of the *XRISM* mission.

KEYWORDS: X-ray Spectroscopy, Atomic Physics, Microcalorimeters

Priyanka Chakraborty

October 31, 2021

EXPLORING THE X-RAY UNIVERSE IN THE MICROCALORIMETER ERA

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To my parents and my fiancé

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I am beyond grateful to my advisor Dr. Gary Ferland. He is the best mentor that one could hope for. I want to thank him for being extremely supportive and incredibly patient all these years during my Ph.D. I also want to thank him for offering me such an exciting research project for my Ph.D. thesis, and providing me the opportunity to learn from his wealth of knowledge. I couldn't have done this thesis without his constant guidance, encouragement, and insightful feedback. I want to sincerely thank Dr. Marios Chatzikos for his continuous guidance and valuable suggestions in the course of my graduate study, and for supporting me with his NASA grant. I am grateful for his co-mentoring and all his help since the beginning of my research career as a graduate student. I am grateful to Dr. Francisco Guzman for his help and collaboration during the first few years of my Ph.D. I am also thankful to Dr. Yuanyuan Su for her collaboration and insights into the *Hitomi* observations.

I want to thank Dr. Stefano Bianchi and Dr. Andrew Fabian for their collaboration and significant contributions to improving our papers. I want to acknowledge Dr. John Raymond for referring our first two papers and adding significantly to the presentation of our work. I want to thank Dr. Anna Ogorzalek for her helpful suggestions.

My deepest thanks go to my parents for believing in me, and for their unwavering support and love. I would not have made it this far without them. I am incredibly grateful to my fiancé Arnab for his unconditional love, and for being there for me since our undergraduate days. He believed in me and encouraged me at the darkest times of my life. I would also like to thank my friends in Lexington, specially Kaushik, Maggie, Daniela, Lydia, and Katie. Life in this foreign country would have been boring and unbearable without them. I want to mention my cat Mithai too, who

kept me happy and occupied outside of astronomy.

I want to acknowledge support by NSF (1816537, 1910687), NASA (17-ATP17-0141, 19-ATP19-0188), and STScI (HST-AR-15018), and STScI (HST-AR-14556.001-A).

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Chapter 1 Introduction

X-rays are high-energy electromagnetic radiation with energy ranging from 0.1 keV to a few tens of keV. X-ray observations spanning the last few decades have unfolded a wealth of information about the astrophysical objects emitting in the X-rays. Examples are - stars like the sun, supernova remnants, binary stars containing white dwarfs, nuclei of active galaxies, galaxy groups, and clusters of galaxies. High-resolution X-ray observations from these objects enable us to probe their plasma properties- such as temperature, density, velocity, magnetic field, etc.

In the X-ray waveband, important atomic transitions appear as absorption or emission features. These spectral features are produced by the transitions of electrons within atoms (or ions) following the absorption/emission of line photons. It is crucial to understand the underlying atomic processes to interpret high-resolution spectra from astronomical sources. This thesis aims to develop tools, spectral diagnostic methods and explain various atomic physical phenomena to interpret such spectra.

The following subsections in this chapter present a brief introduction and history of X-ray spectroscopy, the beginning of the microcalorimeter era and how it motivates this work, various atomic processes that significantly change the observed X-ray spectra, and improvements to the spectral synthesis code CLOUDY used for all the simulations presented in this thesis.

1.1 Brief History of X-ray spectroscopy:

The study of X-ray emitting objects outside our solar system began in the early 1960s with the discovery of Scorpius X-1 (Giacconi et al., 1962). Following this, the launch of Uhuru in 1970 (Giacconi et al., 1971b) made an outstanding advance in X-ray astronomy leading to the discovery of X-ray binary systems containing an X-ray pulsar, Centaurus X-3, and a stellar-mass black hole, Cygnus X-1 (Oda et al., 1971; Giacconi et al., 1971a). The detection of significant X-ray fluxes from the Seyfert galaxies NGC 4151 and NGC 1275 was also reported (Gursky et al., 1971). *Einstein* (Giacconi et al., 1979), the first fully imaging X-ray observatory, was launched in 1978 and discovered approximately five thousand X-ray emitting sources (Schlegel, 2002). The Solid-state spectrometer (SSS) onboard *Einstein* had the spectral resolving power of $E/\Delta E = 3 - 25$ within the energy range 0.5 – 4.5 keV.

The Advanced Satellite for Cosmology and Astrophysics (*ASCA*), launched in 1993, was the first X-ray mission to provide both spectral energy resolution (~ 120 eV at 6 keV) and spatial resolution (~ 30 arcsec). Following this, NASA's flagship mission *Chandra* and the European Space Agency's (ESA) X-ray space observatory *XMM-Newton* were both launched in 1999. These missions were big steps forward in terms of both spatial and spectral resolution. The advanced CCD Imaging Spectrometer (ACIS) onboard *Chandra* and European Photon Imaging Camera (EPIC) onboard *XMM-Newton* provided a moderate spectral resolving power (like *ASCA* but better than the previous X-ray missions) of $E/\Delta E = 35-50$ at 6 keV, and $E/\Delta E = 50$

at 6.5 keV, respectively. *Chandra* and *XMM-Newton* carry grazing-incidence mirrors consisting of pairs of nested reflecting surfaces offering a superb spatial resolution of ~ 0.5 arcsec and ~ 5 arcsec, respectively. The grating instruments onboard these observatories provide high spectral resolution. The High Energy Transmission Grating Spectrometer (HETGS, 0.5 -10 keV) onboard *Chandra* provides $E/\Delta E$ up to 1000. The Reflection Grating Spectrometer (RGS, 0.35 - 2.5 keV) onboard *XMM-Newton* provides $E/\Delta E$ up to 800. Using the grating technology led to significant improvement in spectral resolution in *Chandra* and *XMM-Newton* compared to the previous X-ray observatories, but it came at the expense of losing almost all directional information of which point on the sky the photons come from.

One of the most remarkable advancements in X-ray spectroscopy instrumentation happened in the late 1980s and 1990s with the development of microcalorimeters. The X-ray Spectrometer (XRS) consisting of 32 micro-calorimeter arrays onboard the *Astro-E* observatory (Kelley et al., 2000), launched in 2000, was supposed to be the first microcalorimeter in space. Unfortunately, *Astro-E* was lost during its launch. *Suzaku* (or *Astro-E2*, Mitsuda et al., 2007), a replacement mission of *Astro-E*, was launched in 2005 and successfully operated for 10 years (2005 - 2015). However, soon after launch, the X-ray microcalorimeter spectrometer (XRS-2) onboard *Suzaku* prematurely lost all its liquid helium due to cooling system malfunctions and ceased operating. The first-ever observation with microcalorimeters was made with the *Hitomi* observatory, which is further discussed in Section 1.3.

1.2 Evolution in detectors

1.2.1 Proportional Counter

Proportional counters were the first X-ray detectors used in astronomy. A proportional counter contains a sealed gas chamber filled with an inert gas, typically neon, argon, krypton, or xenon. X-ray radiation entering the chamber photoionizes the inert gas atoms and generates photoelectrons that produce an amplified electrical pulse at the detector output. This output pulse is proportional to the radiation energy of the incoming X-ray; thus called Proportional Counter. Figure 1.1 shows the artist's impression of Proportional Counter.

The energy resolution of the proportional counter is limited, $\sim 15\%$ at 6 keV. Examples of Proportional Counter detectors are - Imaging Proportional Counter (IPC) in *Einstein*, and Imaging Gas Scintillation Proportional Counters (IGSPC) in *ASCA*.

1.2.2 Charge-Coupled Device (CCD)

A charge-coupled device (CCD) is a detector consisting of an array of pixels. Each pixel consists of a positively charged capacitor attached with a thin wafer of silicon. Radiation from astronomical sources hits the silicon surface and produces photoelectrons, which get collected by the capacitors. The number of photoelectrons accumulated by each capacitor is proportional to the intensity of incident radiation at that location. Each capacitor transfers its accumulated charge to the adjacent capacitor

Figure 1.1: Artist’s impression of a gas proportional counter. Taken from Encyclopedia of Nuclear Energy, 2021.

driven by a control circuit until they are transferred to the last capacitor in the array. The last capacitor is connected to a charge amplifier, which converts the charge into a voltage and stores this information in a computer. The same process is repeated until the information stored in all the arrays has been read out to a sequence of voltages. Figure 1.2 shows a pictorial representation of the CCD working principle. The CCD detectors have much improved energy resolution ($\sim 2\text{-}3\%$) compared to the Proportional Counters. As mentioned in Section 1.1, ACIS onboard *Chandra* and EPIC onboard *XMM-Newton* have CCD detector arrays.

Figure 1.2: Pictorial representation of CCD working principle. Taken from Alfaraj (2017).

1.2.3 Microcalorimeters

One of the most crucial advancements in X-ray astronomy instrumentation happened with the development of microcalorimeter detectors. Microcalorimeters consist of a three-component thermal device - an absorber, a thermistor, and a heat sink. X-ray radiation incident on the absorber generates photoelectrons, which rattle around and

Figure 1.3: Sketch of different components of a microcalorimeter.

raise the temperature of the absorber. The increase in temperature is very small (millikelvin order, hence the name microcalorimeter), which can be recorded in the thermistor. This temperature rise (ΔT) is proportional to the energy of the incident X-ray radiation (E):

$$\Delta T = E/C$$

, where C is the heat capacity of the absorber.

The absorber, together with the thermistor, is called an “X-ray detector”. The heat sink maintains the temperature of the X-ray detector by absorbing the excess heat. Figure 1.3 shows the components of a microcalorimeter¹.

The energy resolution of microcalorimeter detectors can be up to $\sim 0.01\%$, orders of magnitude better than that of CCDs and Proportional Counters. As mentioned in Section 1.1, microcalorimeters were developed in the 1990s, although *Hitomi* made the first-ever observation with microcalorimeters. The future missions *XRISM*, *Athena*, and *Lynx*, will carry microcalorimeter detectors (refer to Section 1.3 for a discussion on these missions).

1.3 The era of microcalorimeters

Microcalorimeter detectors combine the remarkable power of high-resolution X-ray spectroscopy without losing the directional information of the photons. The launch of *Hitomi* on February 17, 2016, was a giant leap forward in X-ray spectroscopy. *Hitomi*’s Soft X-ray Spectrometer (SXS, Kelley et al., 2016) was a non-dispersive spectrometer with a built-in calorimeter instead of the CCDs used in *Chandra* and *XMM-Newton*. SXS achieved a spectral energy resolution of ~ 5 eV. The high spectral resolution allowed the detection of emission lines from metals like iron (including the Fe $K\alpha$ complex), nickel, chromium, and manganese. This was much more detailed than the observations made in the past. However, the spatial resolution of the telescope was limited to ~ 1 arcmin, orders of magnitude more coarse than that of *Chandra* and *XMM-Newton*.

¹https://imagine.gsfc.nasa.gov/educators/lessons/xray_spectra/background-micro.html

Figure 1 shows the artist’s illustration of the *Hitomi* Satellite², and Figure 2 shows the spectra around the FeXXV $K\alpha$ complex observed by *Hitomi* from the outer region of Perseus core.

Figure 1.4: Artist’s illustration of the *Hitomi* satellite.

Hitomi was intended to probe some of the most energetic events in the Universe, including the formation of stars and galaxies, the evolution of galaxy clusters, tracking the particles streaming out of black holes, remnants of supernova explosion, etc. Unfortunately, after roughly a month of operation, the *Hitomi* spacecraft lost contact with the ground.

XRISM, the follow-up *Hitomi* mission planned for launch in early 2023, will continue its legacy by probing the hot and energetic Universe with high-resolution X-ray spectroscopy. *XRISM* will provide similar spectral resolution (5-7 eV) and spatial resolution (arcmin order) to that of *Hitomi* over the bandpass 0.3 - 12 keV. The primary objective of *XRISM* is to resume and recover the science lost with the untimely demise of *Hitomi*.

Following this, the launch of *Athena* in the early 2030s will radically transform the field by offering a spatial resolution of 5 arcsec (~ 20 times better than *XRISM*), similar to *XMM-Newton*) and a spectral energy resolution of 2.5 eV (~ 2 times improved over *XRISM*). With the combination of unprecedented spectral resolution and excellent spatial resolution, *Athena* will map the hot gas structures in the Universe, reveal their physical properties and evolution through cosmic time, and track the growth of supermassive black holes (SMBH). There is a proposed mission, *Lynx*, expected to fly in 2035, which will have a spatial resolution of 0.5 arcsec (10 times better than *Athena* and similar to *Chandra*), an extremely high spectral resolution of ~ 5000 , and a very high effective area (2m^2), allowing faint objects at the edge of the universe to be studied.

The need of the hour is to develop a clear understanding of the atomic physical processes for interpreting the high-resolution X-ray spectra that will be available in the next few decades through *XRISM* and *Athena*. The primary goal of my work is

²https://global.jaxa.jp/projects/sas/astro_h/

to develop an understanding of such processes, and building a comprehensive theory on high-resolution X-ray spectroscopy. The following section briefly discusses various atomic physical phenomena and spectral diagnostic methods necessary to interpret the spectra, which will also be elaborated in later chapters.

Figure 1.5: The full array spectrum of the Perseus core observed by the *Hitomi* observatory. The energy range above 7.5 keV has been shown with a log scale in the top-right box. Taken from Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2016).

1.4 Various atomic processes changing the line spectra

In most cases, X-ray emitting plasmas are either collisionally ionized or photoionized. In a collisionally ionized cloud, ionization or excitation events mostly occur due to electron-ion collisions. In a photoionized cloud, ionization is dominated by the interaction between photons and ions/atoms.

There are four asymptotic limits - Cases A, B, C, and D that describes the line formation processes in collisionally ionized and photoionized cloud for H- and He-like systems in the X-ray regime. These limits were previously studied in the optical, UV, and infrared regimes (Menzel, 1937; Menzel and Baker, 1937; Baker and Menzel, 1938; Baker et al., 1938; Hummer and Storey, 1987; Ferland, 1999; Luridiana et al., 2009) but remained largely unexplored in the X-rays. Case A and C represent the optically thin limit without and with an external radiation source, Case B and D represent the optically thick limit without and with an external radiation source, respectively.

Various atomic physical processes can contribute to the changes in the line intensities in the X-ray spectra. For example, line interlocking and Resonant Auger Destruction, Case A to B or Case C to D transition depending on whether the system is collisionally ionized or photoionized, Electron Scattering Escape, and photoelectric

absorption. All these processes and their effects on the X-ray spectra are elaborated in later chapters.

- In Chapter 2, I show the effects of Li-like iron on the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ line intensities through Resonant Auger Destruction (RAD, e.g. Ross et al. (1978); Band et al. (1990); Ross et al. (1996); Liedahl (2005); Chakraborty et al. (2020b)). This analysis is initially motivated by the Perseus cluster, but has been extended to a wide range of column densities encountered in astrophysics. Line broadening effects by electron scattering is also discussed.
- In Chapter 3, I introduce a novel method of measuring column density from Case A to B (optically thin to thick) transition by comparing the observed spectra by *Hitomi* with simulated spectra using a line-ratio diagnostic (Chakraborty et al., 2020c). I reproduce the *Hitomi* spectra for estimating the net line fluxes for the lines in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex, and ratios with respect to the resonance line (w). I also show the effects of turbulence and metallicity on Fe XXV $K\alpha$ line ratios using the Perseus cluster as a reference.
- In Chapter 4, I discuss various line formation conditions in a photoionized cloud (Chakraborty et al., 2021). I establish the mathematical foundation of Cases A, B, C, and D in an irradiated cloud using the spectral simulation code CLOUDY. I also show the total X-ray emission spectrum for all four cases within the energy range 0.1 - 10 keV at the resolving power of *XRISM*. I also estimate the reduction in resonance line intensity with column density due to a combined effect of electron scattering and partial blockage of continuum pumping, which can be an important tool to measure the column density/optical depth of the cloud.
- In Chapter 5, I extend the theory described in the first three chapters to the soft X-ray limit. I discuss the suppression in soft X-ray lines due to photoelectric absorption and electron scattering. The effects of continuum pumping on the soft X-ray are also discussed. I also show the application to this theory on V1223 Sgr, a class of cataclysmic variable binary star system comparing with the *Chandra* MEG first-order spectra.
- In Chapter 6, I discuss the improvements in the H-like $K\alpha$ energies for elements between Carbon and Zinc for the release version of CLOUDY to meet the spectroscopic challenges of future microcalorimeter missions. This is further elaborated in the next subsection.

1.5 CLOUDY in the microcalorimeter era

The spectral synthesis code CLOUDY (Ferland et al., 2017) was used to simulate the spectra in all our calculations. Historically, CLOUDY made predictions for the X-ray regime but was not designed for high-resolution spectral analysis. I extended

CLOUDY to meet the spectroscopic challenges for the upcoming microcalorimeter missions - *XRISM* and *Athena*. These developments include incorporating precise energies (Chakraborty et al., 2020a), updating the electron collision strengths, and adding electron scattering effects for larger column densities. Chapter 2 discussed the addition of electron scattering effects, Chapter 3 discussed the updates in the collision strengths, and Chapter 6 discussed the improvements in the H-like $K\alpha$ energies. These updated $K\alpha$ energies incorporated in the revised CLOUDY release (C17.03) are 15-4000 times more precise than that of C17.02. These improved energies are in excellent agreement with the experimental data.

Chapter 2 Effects of Fe XXIV Resonant Auger Destruction on Fe XXV $K\alpha$ spectra

2.1 Introduction

The Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex has been a subject of interest in the X-ray community for decades. Observations of the Perseus cluster by Ariel 5 detected an emission feature near 7 keV caused by transitions from Fe XXV and Fe XXVI (Mitchell et al., 1976). The Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex was later detected at 6.7 keV by XMM-Newton (Churazov et al., 2004). Recently, the Soft X-ray Spectrometer (SXS, Kelley et al., 2016) on board *Hitomi* resolved the complex into four components – the resonance (w), intercombination (x,y), and forbidden (z) lines (Hitomi Collaboration et al., 2016). Some previous studies of X-ray emission by He-like iron are Bautista and Kallman (2000), and Mehdipour et al. (2015), and by Porquet and Dubau (2000), and Smith et al. (2001) for lighter elements.

In the higher column density limit, two atomic processes contribute to the change in intensity of line photons in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. First, line photons are absorbed by satellites of three- electron iron and He-like chromium due to line interlocking and lose their identities (see section 2.4, 2.5). Second, Lyman line photons are absorbed by Fe XXV itself following the emission of different line photons (Case A to B transition), as discussed in the second paper of this series (Chakraborty et al., 2020, hereafter paper II). However, it is difficult to decouple these two processes and study them independently. This Chapter focuses on the importance of line interlocking in deciding Fe XXV $K\alpha$ line intensities using the spectral synthesis code CLOUDY (Ferland et al., 2017), with occasional references to the Case A to B transition.

We explore the effects of Resonant Auger Destruction (RAD), line absorption by satellites leading to autoionization, originally introduced by Band et al. (1990). The term RAD was introduced by Ross et al. (1996) and more recently has been reviewed by Liedahl (2005). These papers show that it is very important in explaining the intensities of certain lines in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. Although we do all our calculations using the physical parameters for the Perseus core, which is optically thin for x, y, and z, RAD only becomes important in the high-column-density limit. This is a spectral analysis in the column density parameter space, extended up to hydrogen column density $N_{\text{H}}=10^{25} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, typically encountered in astronomy. Although such high column densities do not occur in the Perseus intracluster medium, they do happen in other environments, such as accretion disks, Compton thick regions, Fe $K\alpha$ fluorescent emission line in active galactic nuclei, and some Seyfert galaxies (Matt et al., 1996; Bianchi and Matt, 2002; Bianchi et al., 2005; Yaqoob and Murphy, 2011; Yaqoob, 2012; Marin et al., 2013; Tzanavaris et al., 2019) which CLOUDY can model. We document the full physical treatment for future reference.

In addition, at hydrogen column densities higher than $N_{\text{H}}=10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, electron scattering opacity starts to become important. Line photons scatter off thermal electrons and become heavily Doppler shifted, leading to one-scattering escape. We

call this process Electron Scattering Escape (ESE). This causes a deficit in the line intensity at the wavelength of the scattered photons. We elaborate on this process in section 2.7.

The organization of this Chapter is as follows. Section 3.2 lists the various atomic data sources used in our calculations. Section 3.5 discusses the parameters used for our simulations with CLOUDY. Section 2.4 discusses the physics of line interlocking. Section 2.5 demonstrates autoionization following the absorption of Fe XXV $K\alpha$ line photons. Section 2.6 discusses the spectroscopic evidence of RAD in selective Fe XXV $K\alpha$ line photons. Section 2.7 describes the change in Fe XXV $K\alpha$ line intensities due to Electron Scattering Escape. Section 2.8 summarizes our results.

2.2 Atomic data

This section describes the various atomic data sources we use in our spectral modeling. Our calculations are very wavelength sensitive and require a precise atomic dataset for the accurate prediction of spectral behavior in the high-column-density limit. Atomic data sources for He-like iron (Fe^{24+}) are discussed in paper II. Atomic data sources for the two ions contributing to line interlocking with Fe^{24+} : Fe^{23+} and Cr^{22+} (for hydrogen column densities higher than 10^{23} cm^{-2}) are discussed below.

2.2.1 Energy Levels

The previous version of CLOUDY (Ferland et al., 2017) used Fe^{23+} and Cr^{22+} energy levels calculated using the code Autostructure, as described in Badnell et al. (2005). We replace these with CHIANTI version 9.0 (Dere et al., 2019, 1997), which uses a more recent Autostructure calculation (Badnell, 2011). The process of “line interlocking” described in section 2.4 is very sensitive to the line wavelengths, as even a slight variation in the energy levels can significantly change the line-center optical depths. We find that the uncertainty in Fe^{23+} is particularly important for our analysis. See section 2.8 for a brief discussion on how uncertainties in energy levels or velocity fields can alter the nature of the spectra in high column densities.

2.2.2 Transition Probabilities

For transitions between autoionizing levels and ground in Fe^{23+} , we use transition probabilities from CHIANTI version 9.0, which are taken from Autostructure calculations. Table 2.1 gives the list of transition probabilities used in our calculation near the energy range of the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. We found a swap between two Fe XXIV lines in the NIST atomic database (Kramida et al., 2018), which can significantly alter the line-center optical depth in x, as well as the calculations for RAD. This issue is further addressed in section 2.8.

2.2.3 Autoionization rates

We use autoionization rates of autoionizing energy levels in Fe^{23+} from Autostructure (Badnell, 2011). The list of autoionization rates for the energy levels near Fe XXV

Table 2.1: Energy level configurations, labels, corresponding wavelengths, downward transition probabilities ($A_{u,l}$), and autoionization rates (A_a) (if applicable) for transitions from the ground in Fe^{24+} generating Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex, and in Fe^{23+} , Fe^{22+} , and Cr^{22+} in the proximity of the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex.

Ion	Configuration	Label	Wavelength(\AA)	$A_{u,l}(\text{s}^{-1})$	$A_a(\text{s}^{-1})$
Fe^{24+}	$1s.2p \ ^1P_1$	w	1.8504	4.54e+14	-
	$1s.2p \ ^3P_2$	x	1.8554	6.30e+09	-
	$1s.2p \ ^3P_1$	y	1.8595	4.11e+13	-
	$1s.2s \ ^3S_1$	z	1.8682	2.15e+08	-
Fe^{23+}	$1s.2s.2p \ ^2P_{3/2}$	-	1.8563	3.420e+12	1.09e+14
	$1s.2s.2p \ ^2P_{1/2}$	-	1.8571	1.900e+14	7.58e+13
	$1s.2s.2p \ ^2P_{3/2}$	-	1.8610	4.680e+14	2.90e+09
	$1s.2s.2p \ ^2P_{1/2}$	-	1.8636	2.920e+14	3.38e+13
Cr^{22+}	$1s.3p \ ^1P_1$	-	1.8558	8.970e+13	-
Fe^{22+}	$1s.2s2.2p \ ^1P_1$	-	1.8704	4.210e+14	5.56e+12

$K\alpha$ energies is given in Table 2.1.

2.3 Simulation Parameters

For our simulation with CLOUDY, we use the temperature, metal abundance, and turbulence in Perseus core. Although the hydrogen column density reported by Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018a) ($N_{\text{H}} \sim 1.88 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) is too small in Perseus to show the effects of RAD, we extend our parameter space up to a hydrogen column density $N_{\text{H}} = 10^{25} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. This is to document models of optically thick environments to which CLOUDY can be applied. We choose the temperature and Fe abundance in the interval $4.05^{+0.01}_{-0.01} \text{ keV}$ and $0.65^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$ of solar, respectively, following the *Hitomi* observations (Hitomi Collaboration et al., 2018b) from a broad-band fit in the energy range 1.8–20.0 keV. We assume an average hydrogen density of 0.03 cm^{-3} in our region of interest, and a chromium to iron abundance ratio ~ 0.15 . Although the Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018b) reported a slight difference in turbulent broadening between w (159–167 km/s) and x, y, z (136–150 km/s) in the outer core of Perseus, we use a turbulent velocity of 150 km/s in our simulation for simplicity.

2.4 Loss of identity via “Line interlocking”

The total optical depth of the cloud determines the radiative transfer effects in line photons like absorption by ions of the same/ different element, or the Case A to B transfer (see paper II). A photon within a line simply scatters off the total opacity that is present in the gas. It has no knowledge of which transition or species created that opacity. This scattering produces “line interlocking” where a photon can change its identity. This process is described, for instance, in Elitzur and Netzer (1985) and Netzer et al. (1985).

Figure 2.1: a) Total optical depth for a cloud with a hydrogen column density of 10^{25} cm^{-2} plotted as a function of wavelength in Å. Solid and dashed lines show our best model and the best model without Electron Scattering Escape (ESE), respectively. The vertical lines above the blue curve mark the wavelengths of w, x, y, and z. Individual lines with a single-line optical depth ≥ 1 , are marked with vertical lines below the grey dashed curve. b) Variation of total line-center optical depth, and single-line optical depth for x, y, z, and w with hydrogen column density for our best model. Solid lines show the total line-center optical depths, and dashed lines show single-line optical depths for these lines. Slower than linear increase in the total line-center optical depths in x, y, and z photons in the high-column-density limit is due to the decline in the Fe^{23+} and Fe^{22+} concentration following autoionization and RAD.

CLOUDY handles line overlap with a “fine opacity” grid that is described by Shaw et al. (2005). The left panel of Figure 2.1 shows this fine opacity grid in the spectral region near Fe XXV $K\alpha$ for $N_{\text{H}} = 10^{25}$ cm^{-2} , the upper limit of column density used in our calculations. For w, the total line-center optical depth solely comes from its single-line optical depth. But x, y, and z have contributions from other lines. The dominant contributions to the total optical depth at the center of x are from Fe XXIV ($\lambda=1.8571\text{\AA}$) and Cr XXIII ($\lambda=1.8558\text{\AA}$) satellites, and z is from Fe XXIII ($\lambda=1.8704\text{\AA}$). y has a small contribution from the Fe XXIV satellite ($\lambda=1.8610\text{\AA}$). Electron Scattering Escape (ESE) also becomes important at such a high column density. The Figure shows the variation of the total line-center optical depth with wavelength for our best model and a model without ESE with solid and dashed lines, respectively.

The right panel of Figure 2.1 shows the contrast between the single-line and total line-center optical depths of x, y, z, w for our best model, and their variation with column density. The single-line optical depths in x and z significantly differ from that of their line-center optical depths. This difference is a result of absorption of x and z photons by Fe^{23+} and Cr^{22+} , and Fe^{22+} respectively at the wavelengths mentioned in the previous paragraph. The total line-center optical depth in y has a relatively

Figure 2.2: Left: Partial energy level diagram of one-, two-, three-, and four-electron iron. The red dashed line marks the energy of the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. Right: Enlarged energy diagram of Fe^{22+} , Fe^{23+} , Fe^{24+} , and Cr^{22+} near Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. Red, blue, green, and magenta lines mark the upper energy level of w, x, y, and z transition.

smaller deviation from its single-line optical depth. This happens due to absorption by Fe^{23+} . There is an overlap between the two optical depths in w as expected, with zero absorption by other ions.

The total line-center optical depth shows a linear increase with column density for w. However, x, y, and z show a slightly slower than linear increase in their total line-center optical depth with column density in the high-column-density limit. Such deviations from linearity are caused by a decline in the Fe^{23+} and Fe^{22+} concentration through RAD (Liedahl, 2005). See the next section for further discussion.

2.5 Autoionization following absorption

As a direct consequence of “line interlocking”, a line photon emitted by one ion can be absorbed by another ion of the same/different element with approximately the same energy. This section discusses the atomic processes following absorption of the lines in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex by various ions, while section 2.6 explores the changes in Fe XXV $K\alpha$ line intensities due to the absorption.

The left panel of Figure 2.2 shows the energy levels for one-, two-, three-, and four-electron iron. The red dashed line marks the energy of the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. The Figure shows a clear proximity of selected Fe^{22+} and Fe^{23+} energy levels to the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ energies. These energy levels lie well above the ionization limits of three-, and four-electron iron, hence are autoionizing levels. An enlarged version near the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ energies is shown in the right panel of Figure 2.2. An additional

Figure 2.3: Absolute line intensities for the members of the Fe XXV K α complex with respect to hydrogen column density.

column showing the energy levels in Cr²²⁺ is included in the enlarged version as the x line-center optical depth has contributions from a Cr XXIII transition too (see section 2.4). The probability of a Fe XXV K α line photon being absorbed by other ions depends on two factors. First, whether the energy levels of the absorbing ion are similar to the emitted line photon to allow line interlocking. The right panel of Figure 2.2 gives a visual illustration of the proximity in energy levels in different ions. Second, if the optical depth for that transition is large enough for the absorption to happen, where optical depth is given by the equation:

$$\tau_{\nu}(x) = 2.24484 \times 10^{-14} A_{u,l} \lambda_{\mu m}^3 \frac{g_u \varphi_{\nu}(x)}{g_l u_{Dop}} N_{ion} \quad (2.1)$$

Once absorbed, the excited ion may or may not undergo autoionization. The probability of autoionization depends on the following ratio: $p_a = \frac{A_a}{(A_a + A_{u,l})}$, where A_a is the autoionization rate of the upper level of the excited ion, and $A_{u,l}$ is the downward radiative transition probability. For light elements like helium, p_a is usually close to 1. In heavier elements like iron, p_a can be as small as $\sim 10^{-5}$ for some levels. Table 2.1 gives the list of $A_{u,l}$, and A_a for the Fe²³⁺, Cr²²⁺, Fe²²⁺ energy levels in close proximity to the Fe XXV K α energies, and the list of $A_{u,l}$ for Fe²⁴⁺ generating the Fe XXV K α complex.

The total x line-center optical depth becomes ≥ 1 only for hydrogen column densities - $N_H \geq 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The transition wavelengths in the proximity of x ($\lambda = 1.8554 \text{ \AA}$) are: two Fe XXIV ($\lambda = 1.8563 \text{ \AA}$, 1.8571 \AA), and one Cr XXIII ($\lambda = 1.8558 \text{ \AA}$) satellite lines. Among these, one of the Fe XXIV satellite ($\lambda = 1.8563 \text{ \AA}$) has a negligible contribution in the absorption of x due to its small $A_{u,l}$ (see table 2.1). The transitions dominating absorption of x are therefore Fe XXIV ($\lambda = 1.8571 \text{ \AA}$), and Cr XXIII ($\lambda =$

Figure 2.4: Top: Variation of x/w , y/w , and z/w with hydrogen column density for our best model, and a model excluding Fe^{23+} . Bottom: Variation of the ratios of our best model to the model without Fe^{23+} for x/w , y/w , and z/w with hydrogen column density.

1.8558Å). The former has $p_a = 0.29$, while the latter has $p_a \sim 10^{-2}$ for one scattering. Therefore, in the instances of a single absorption by Fe^{23+} corresponding to $\lambda = 1.8571\text{Å}$, approximately one-third of Fe^{23+} will autoionize destroying the absorbed x photons, causing a deficit in the x line intensity. If absorbed by Cr^{22+} , the ion will most likely de-excite by the emission of a line photon of the same wavelength having no effect on the x line intensity.

In contrast, the line-center optical depth in y ($\lambda = 1.8595\text{Å}$) has a small contribution from the Fe XXIV satellite at the wavelength 1.8610Å with $p_a \sim 10^{-5}$. Even though a small fraction of y is absorbed by Fe^{23+} , the autoionization probability is negligible. Up to very high column densities ($N_H \leq 10^{25} \text{cm}^{-2}$) the line-center optical depth in z remains < 1 . Thus, the absorption of z photons ($\lambda = 1.8682\text{Å}$) does not become important despite its proximity with the Fe XXIII satellite line at $\lambda = 1.8704\text{Å}$. Beyond this column density, however, some z photons will be absorbed by Fe^{22+} , with a very small probability of autoionization and loss of z photon ($p_a \sim 10^{-2}$).

The loss of line photons following autoionization is referred to as Resonant Auger Destruction (RAD) in Ross et al. (1996) and Liedahl (2005). This not only leads to suppression of selective line intensities in the high column density (see the next section) but also causes the absorbing ion concentration to decrease due to autoionization. The higher the p_a , the higher the number of RAD and the more pronounced

this effect will be. That is why the x line-center optical depth shows a clear slower-than-linear growth in the high column density range ($N_H \geq 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) in the right panel of Figure 2.1, while y only slightly deviates. In the very high column density ($N_H \geq 10^{25} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), line-center optical depth in z shows a slight slower-than-linear growth due to absorption by Fe^{22+} , following RAD.

2.6 Spectroscopic Evidence of RAD

The continuous increase in the line intensities with column density makes it difficult to detect where the redistribution in photon energy is happening via absorption/re-emission (see Figure 2.3). Such effects can be best demonstrated with a line-ratio diagnostic instead.

We plot the variation of x, y, z line intensities relative to w versus hydrogen column density in Figure 2.4. As the total-line-center optical depth in w comes entirely from its single-line optical depth, absorption by other ions does not have any effect on its line intensity. The amount of change in the line ratios of x, y, and z relative to w will, therefore, only be subject to the change in the numerator intensities due to absorption by ions.

In the low-column-density limit, all the lines in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex are optically thin. Line photons emitted in the cloud escape. Without absorption by ions, the line intensities increase with column density. The line ratios, therefore, remain unchanged in the low-column-density limit. In the high-column-density limit, two atomic processes simultaneously change the line intensities of the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex: absorption of line photons following line interlocking, and the transfer from Case A to B. The former is studied in this Chapter, while the latter is the subject of the following Chapter. Besides, in the very high-column-density limit ($N_H \geq 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), ESE also starts to become important.

Section 2.4 discussed the contribution of absorption by Fe^{23+} in deciding the line-center optical depth in x and y. CLOUDY normally determines the population of various ion stages self consistently. To test the role of Fe^{23+} , we artificially set the abundance of Fe^{23+} to a very small value and compared it with an all-ion-inclusive model. The top panel of Figure 2.4 compares the x/w, y/w, and z/w ratios with and without Fe^{23+} .

The top-left panel of the Figure compares the x/w ratios with and without Fe^{23+} . The change in the x line intensity for our best model (with Fe^{23+}) comes from the Case A to B transition, line interlocking with Fe^{23+} , and ESE (see section 2.7), and other factors mentioned in the appendix. The Case A to B transition causes all 2 \rightarrow 1 line intensities, and therefore the line ratios, to increase (see section 6.2 in paper II). We find the increase in x/w due to Case A to B transfer to be small. The decrease in the x/w ratio with column density in the Fe^{23+} inclusive model is partly due to interactions with Fe^{23+} . As w is not affected by Fe^{23+} , the decrease in the x/w line ratio in the presence of Fe^{23+} only reflects the deficit in x line photons at the higher column densities. According to our calculations, $\sim 32\%$ of x photons are lost due to absorption by Fe^{23+} at the hydrogen column density 10^{25} cm^{-2} .

Analytically, the fraction of photons destroyed due to RAD depends on the downward radiative transition probability ($A_{u,l}$), and autoionization rate of the upper level (A_a). When the x photon is absorbed by Fe^{23+} , corresponding to the wavelength 1.8571\AA , the fraction of x photons destroyed in one scattering is: $p_a = \frac{A_a}{(A_a + A_{u,l})} = 0.29$ as discussed in the previous section. The optical depth contribution at the line center of x due to line interlocking with the $\lambda = 1.8571\text{\AA}$ transition is ~ 1 at the hydrogen column density of 10^{25} cm^{-2} . This implies that $\sim 29\%$ of the x photons are destroyed at $N_{\text{H}} = 10^{25} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The analytical theory of RAD is, therefore, consistent with our calculation, which predicts a 32% deficit in x line intensity at the same hydrogen column density.

For the sake of simplicity in the demonstration, we compare the analytical and calculated values for the decrease in x line intensity due to RAD at the hydrogen column density 10^{25} cm^{-2} . RAD in x however, begins at a much lower hydrogen column density ($N_{\text{H}} = 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). The percentage of x photons destroyed at the hydrogen column densities 10^{23} cm^{-2} , 10^{24} cm^{-2} , 10^{25} cm^{-2} are $\sim 2\text{-}3\%$, $\sim 12\%$, and $\sim 32\%$, respectively. The bottom panel of Figure 2.4 shows the variation of the ratios of x/w, y/w, and z/w for our best model to the model without Fe^{23+} with hydrogen column density.

The upper middle panel of Figure 2.4 compares the y/w ratio for our best model and a model excluding Fe^{23+} . Unlike x, the presence of Fe^{23+} slightly alters y line intensity ($\leq 2\%$). This is expected, as the line-center optical depth in y has much smaller contribution from Fe XXIV ($\lambda = 1.8610\text{\AA}$), with $p_a \sim 10^{-2}$. The slight increase in y/w in the high column density happens due to Case A to B transfer and will be addressed in paper II.

The right panel of Figure 2.4 compares the z/w ratio with and without Fe^{23+} . As the presence of Fe^{23+} does not make z optically thick even at our highest column density limit ($N_{\text{H}} = 10^{25} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), ideally z line intensity should remain the same for the with or without Fe^{23+} models. However, both plots in the right panel show a small increase in the z/w ratio ($\sim 2\%$) in the presence of Fe^{23+} . This behavior is opposite to that of x/w indicating that the number of x photons lost is converted to z photons causing z/w to increase in the with Fe^{23+} model. This is Case A to B behavior discussed in detail in paper II, and points towards the conversion of a tiny fraction of x photons into z photons.

2.7 Electron scattering escape

2.7.1 General Formalism

The mean number of scatterings (N) experienced by a line photon before escaping an optically thick cloud is related to its line-center optical depth (τ) with the following equation (Ferland and Netzer, 1979):

$$N = \begin{cases} 1.11\tau^{0.826} & \text{if } \tau < 1 \\ \frac{1.11\tau^{1.071}}{1+(\log\tau/5.5)^5} & \text{if } \tau \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

Notice that the number of scatterings is nearly linear in τ and is not proportional to τ^2 , as would occur if it did a random walk in space.

CLOUDY uses the formalism developed by Hummer and Kunasz (1980) in treating energy loss during resonance scattering. This treatment does apply to Fe K α since the range of damping constants they consider does extend up to the very large values ($a \sim 0.045$ for w) found in allowed X-ray transitions. This theory predicts a modest increase in path length, which is taken into account.

The presence of fast thermal electrons in the cloud may lead to one-scattering-escape in some fraction of the line photons. This happens when line photons receive a large Doppler shift from their line-center upon scattering off high-speed electrons. The probability of scattering off electrons is given by the following:

$$P_{\text{broad}} = \frac{\kappa_e}{\kappa_{\text{tot}}} \quad (2.3)$$

where κ_e is the electron scattering opacity, and κ_{tot} is the total line-center opacity at that wavelength. κ_{tot} includes total line opacity (κ_{line}) and continuous opacity (κ_{con}). The latter includes electron scattering (κ_e), photoelectric absorption, and dust opacity (if dust is present)¹.

The fraction of photons escaping the cloud after N scattering is :

$$f_{\text{ese}} = 1 - (1 - P_{\text{broad}})^N. \quad (2.4)$$

We name this process of photon escape following a single event of scattering off electron- “Electron Scattering Escape (ESE)”.

At the Perseus core temperature, the velocity of an electron is mildly relativistic (~ 37200 km/s), about 15% of the speed of light. The ratio of electron to iron thermal widths is $\sqrt{m_{\text{Fe}}/m_e} \sim 300$. When the photons scatter off such high-speed electrons, they are Doppler shifted far away from the line center and escape the cloud. This leads to the broadening of Gaussian line profiles with a super-broad-base under Fe XXV K α of ~ 1 keV width. This is a line broadening process that can be observed only in the high-column-density limit with an optically thick cloud. Therefore, Perseus is not subject to line broadening due to ESE. But optically thick environments such as accretion disks will show such line broadening.

ESE depends on the two following factors: the probability of being scattered by electrons (P_{broad}), and the mean number of scatterings (N) experienced by the line photons (see equation 2.4). The single-line opacities (κ_{line}) in x, y, and z are smaller

1

We evaluate equation 3, assuming that the line opacity does not depend on optical depth. This is equivalent to assuming that the opacity does not depend on frequency. This is true for electron scattering since the Klein-Nishina cross-section varies very slowly with energy. The K α line opacity has an energy dependence given by the Voigt function. Lines that scatter in the core of the profile undergo complete redistribution where the absorbed and emitted photon energy is uncorrelated. This leads to a frequency-independent source function, one that is constant across the Doppler width. Thus, to a fair approximation, we can evaluate the line opacity and assume that the ratio given in equation 3 does not depend on optical depth. We know of no numerical calculations of transport of strongly damped lines with background opacity, other than the Hummer and Kunasz (1980) work, which considers only larger optical depths. Such calculations should be done in support of future microcalorimeters missions.

than that of w. Their P_{broad} values are larger, which makes them more likely to suffer electron scattering. But w has a much (~ 100 or higher) larger mean number of scatterings N , which tends to increase the possibility of ESE, but its much larger κ_{line} makes P_{broad} smaller, which tends to decrease ESE. This complex interplay between N and P_{broad} causes changes in the line profiles in x, y, z, and w. However, this does not change the line intensities in x, y, z, or w. The Gaussian line profiles get broader and flatter due to ESE, keeping the area under the Gaussian and the intensity constant. We show the ratio of the total line intensities under the Gaussians in Figure 2.5. The line intensities (and the line ratios), although independent of ESE in x, y, z, and, w, depend on the following factors:

First, ESE in other line photons can cause the line intensities in x, y, z, and w to change. Figure 2.5 compares the line ratios with respect to w with and without ESE for the following cases: a) in an all-ion-inclusive model /our best model, and b) for a model excluding Fe^{23+} . In the optically thick (Case B) limit, higher n Lyman lines are converted to Balmer plus Ly- α photons, causing an overall increase in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex line intensities (paper II). Higher- n Lyman lines have smaller κ_{line} , and so have a higher probability of being scattered by electrons according to equation 5.4. A fraction of the higher- n Lyman lines will, therefore, escape the cloud through ESE before being converted to Ly- α . This will result in a net decrease in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex line intensities, which will weaken the weak $n = 2 \rightarrow 1$ transitions (x, y, z) more than w, the strongest. This explains the overall decrease in x/w, y/w, and z/w line ratios in Figure 2.5 in the presence of ESE.

Second, the presence of ESE can slightly increase the line intensity in x. The x photons that escape the cloud following electron scattering will not be subject to absorption by Fe^{23+} . Thus ESE in x photons reduces the effect of RAD on x line intensity. This implies that the intensity of x line photons in our best model including ESE will be slightly enhanced compared to the without ESE model. The line intensity change in Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex due to ESE is collectively determined by ESE of higher n Lyman line photons and weakening of RAD effects in x photons. Figure 2.5 reflects all these contributions.

Note that our best model in the Figure calculates line intensities including the super-broad-base under the Gaussian. Each Gaussian in our best model consists of two components. A broad line component generating from ESE, and a narrow line component for the photons not scattered away from the line-center. A high-resolution X-ray telescope will only detect the narrow line component. But a low-resolution telescope with a resolution equivalent to 1 keV will detect the narrow and broad line components together. The difference in telescope resolution will, therefore, detect different line fluxes in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. In the next subsection, we discuss the variation of line ratios with column densities for the narrow line component, as a high-resolution X-ray telescope will observe it.

2.7.2 What will be observed?

From the view of high-resolution X-ray spectroscopy, like *Chandra* HETG, or future observations by *XRISM* or *Athena*, photons that suffer ESE are lost from the Fe XXV

Figure 2.5: Left, middle and right panels show the variation of x/w , y/w , and z/w with respect to the hydrogen column density for our best model and a Fe²³⁺ exclusive model, with and without ESE. The best model consists of a narrow line component and a broad line component coming from ESE.

Figure 2.6: Left, middle, and right panels show the variation of x/w , y/w , and z/w with respect to the hydrogen column density for narrow + broad line, and narrow line components. The total effective intensity of the lines in the Fe XXV K α complex (and the line ratios) consists of the narrow + broad line component and is the same as the best model shown in Figure 2.5. The broad line component comes from ESE and has a spread of ~ 1 keV. The narrow line component does not include the photons scattered by electrons and is the only line component detected by microcalorimeters/high-resolution X-ray telescopes. The low-resolution telescopes will detect the narrow and broad line components together.

$K\alpha$ complex. Figure 2.6 shows the line ratios that will be observed in high-resolution. This is different from Figure 2.5, which included the electron-scattered Fe XXV $K\alpha$ photons and the super-broad-base of the Gaussian in the calculation of line intensities (and line ratios).

Let us analytically estimate the reduction in w line intensity in the observed high-resolution spectra due to the migration of w photons away from its line-center, following ESE. The probability (P_{broad}) that w suffers ESE and is lost from the observed spectra is given by equation 5.4. The probability that the w photons will be emitted as a sharp/narrow w line is given by : $P_{\text{narrow}}=1/N$ (N is calculated from equation 5.2). This narrow line intensity will be detected in the high-resolution spectra. At $N_{\text{H}}=10^{25} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, we find that : $P_{\text{broad}} \sim 5 \times P_{\text{narrow}}$. This implies that the observed w line intensity at $N_{\text{H}}=10^{25} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ should be 5 times smaller than its optically thin limit where the line photons are not subject to ESE. The increase in x/w , y/w , and z/w in Figure 2.6 partly comes from this reduction of w intensity in the observed high-resolution spectra. The net variation in the line ratios in the Figure is also partly due to a reduction in x , y , and z intensity in the high-resolution observed spectra, and other factors contributing to the line intensity change explained in Section 2.7.1.

2.8 Summary

This paper discusses the significance of three-electron iron in deciding the line intensities of the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. We explore the effects of Resonant Auger Destruction (RAD) with CLOUDY initially motivated by the Perseus cluster. We extend our analysis to the wide range of column densities we encounter in astrophysics to which CLOUDY can be applied. We summarize our results below:

- Whether a line photon escapes the cloud without scattering or is absorbed by ions of the same/different elements depends on its line-center optical depth. The total line-center optical depth corresponding to a transition can entirely come from that transition itself or may have contributions from other transitions of the same/different element. A photon within a line scatters off due to the total opacity, with no knowledge of which transition or species created that opacity. This leads to line interlocking with the possible loss of identity of the absorbed photon. Among the four members in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex, the x line-center optical depth has significant contributions from single line optical depths of selected Fe XXIV ($\lambda=1.8571\text{\AA}$), and Cr XXIII ($\lambda=1.8558\text{\AA}$) satellites in very high column densities. y and z have contributions from Fe XXIV ($\lambda=1.8610\text{\AA}$), and Fe XXIII ($\lambda=1.8704\text{\AA}$) satellites, respectively. The line-center opacity in w is the same as its single-line opacity, and hence is unaffected.
- Upon absorption by Fe^{23+} , x photons excite Fe^{23+} to the autoionizing level $1s.2s({}^3S).2p {}^2P_{1/2}$ (corresponding to $\lambda=1.8571\text{\AA}$). Theoretically, $\sim 29\%$ of the x photon should be destroyed in one scattering/ for the optical depth of unity due to RAD. Our calculations show very good agreement with theory. At

the hydrogen column density of 10^{25} cm^{-2} , the optical depth contribution at the line center of x from line interlocking with $\lambda = 1.8571 \text{ \AA}$ transition is ~ 1 . At the same hydrogen column density, we see a deficit of $\sim 32\%$ in the x line intensity in the presence of Fe^{23+} compared to the case with Fe^{23+} removed for our best model. The change in x line intensity due to RAD, however, begins at a much lower hydrogen column density ($N_{\text{H}} = 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). The percentage of x photons destroyed at the hydrogen column densities 10^{23} cm^{-2} , 10^{24} cm^{-2} , and 10^{25} cm^{-2} are $\sim 2\text{-}3\%$, $\sim 12\%$, and $\sim 32\%$, respectively.

A small fraction of y photons excite Fe^{23+} from the ground state to $1s.2s({}^3S).2p {}^2P_{3/2}$ ($\lambda = 1.8610 \text{ \AA}$), but rarely get destroyed in RAD, because the autoionizing rate of the excited level is $\sim 10^{-5}$ times smaller than the downward transition probability. z photons do not exhibit line interlocking with any Fe XXIV photons, and therefore the z line intensity is not directly affected by RAD.

- Line photons can become heavily Doppler-shifted from their line-center upon after scattering off fast thermal electrons that are present in the cloud. This leads to one-scattering-escape for a fraction of line photons, a process we call Electron Scattering Escape (ESE). Line broadening through this process becomes very important at high column densities. In the high-column-density limit, ESE can lead to a super-broad-base under Fe XXV $K\alpha$ of $\sim 1 \text{ keV}$ width. The effective intensity of each line in the $K\alpha$ complex consists of a narrow line component and a broad line component coming from ESE. High-resolution X-ray telescopes like *XRISM* and *Athena* will only detect the narrow line component, whereas low-resolution telescopes will detect both the narrow and broad line components. The line fluxes detected by high- and low-resolution telescopes will, therefore, be different.
- Line interlocking processes are very sensitive to line wavelengths. A change of $\sim 0.02\%$ in the wavelengths can significantly alter the line interlocking processes, as well as the nature of line intensities of Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. In addition, the optical depth of a line with similar energy as that of Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex determines the degree of interlocking, making the accurate reporting of transition probabilities in the various atomic data sets extremely important. We found a swap in the transition probabilities between the two Fe XXIV lines ($\lambda = 1.8563 \text{ \AA}$, $\lambda = 1.8610 \text{ \AA}$) in NIST. A swap in the transition probabilities will significantly change the x line-center optical depth, and change the hydrogen column density to 10^{24} cm^{-2} where we see a $\sim 50\%$ decrease in x intensity due to RAD. We verified this mistake with the NIST team, and use CHIANTI version 9.0 instead for both wavelengths and transition probabilities in our calculation.
- Although we assume a static geometry in this paper, we point out that the physics of RAD provides a diagnostic indicator of velocity gradients. The left panel of Figure 2.4 shows a deficit of $\sim 32\%$ in x line intensity in the presence of Fe^{23+} due to RAD, as compared to the case without Fe^{23+} . In our calculations for a static geometry, the artificial removal of Fe^{23+} from our model negates

the effects of RAD. But in a dynamic cloud, a velocity gradient between the Fe^{23+} and Fe^{24+} -emitting regions can also decrease/remove the RAD effects. For instance, if the Fe^{23+} gas were moving by one or more thermal velocities relative to the Fe^{24+} gas, there will be no overlap and no RAD. Such diagnostics will provide a possible indicator of the velocity gradients.

- The ratio of Fe^{23+} to Fe^{24+} abundance depends on the temperature of the plasma (Nikolić et al., 2013). This ratio is higher in the low-temperature limit. Therefore, the effects of line interlocking and RAD can be observed at much lower column densities in the systems cooler than Perseus. In such systems, there may be significant contributions from Fe^{23+} and other satellite lines to what appears to be the x, y, and z.
- Our model assumes a symmetric emitting region, but the combination of asymmetry with the high w line optical depth will increase or decrease w relative to the other lines, as described by Gilfanov et al. (1987), and paper II.

2.9 Appendices

2.9.1 The physics of the x transition

In this Chapter, we discussed the effects of Fe^{23+} and ESE in deciding the x/w ratio. However, two other factors change the line intensity in x — line interlocking of x with Cr^{22+} and broadband electron scattering (BES). Figure 2.5 considers the effects of Fe^{23+} and ESE. Figure 2.7 considers these processes in addition to Cr^{22+} and broadband electron scattering (BES).

The best model is shown in black and discussed above. That discussion also considered the Fe^{23+} and ESE, which are shown with the red and blue lines. We found that x overlaps with a line of Cr XXIII, which produces additional RAD destruction. This was removed in the green line. Finally, broadband electron scattering traps some line radiation, which produces photoionization, and changes the ionization of the gas. This was removed in the magenta line. Together these processes account for the decrease in x in Figure 2.7.

2.9.2 New Cloudy commands

Starting in CLOUDY version 17.03, ESE can be switched off using the command:

```
no scattering escape physics
```

We exclude the effects of ESE in Figure 2.5 with this command.

In the presence of ESE, there will be a narrow and broad line component in each Gaussian in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. Only the narrow line components will be detected in the high-resolution telescopes. The narrow components from each Gaussian can be extracted with CLOUDY using the command:

```
no scattering escape intensity
```


Figure 2.7: The variation of x/w with hydrogen column density for a step by step removal of Fe^{23+} , electron scattering escape (ESE), Chromium, and broadband electron scattering (BES) from our best model.

in the input script. This is a change from the older version of CLOUDY that only had the `no scattering escape` command.

Chapter 3 A new Diagnostic on Column Density from the Case A to B Transition in H- and He-like Iron

3.1 Introduction

Galaxy clusters are the largest gravitationally bound objects in the Universe. Due to X-ray emission from the hot ($10^7 - 10^8\text{K}$) intracluster medium (ICM), they serve as excellent probes of gas dynamics (Sarazin, 2008; Elmegreen et al., 2009; McCourt, 2014; Planelles et al., 2016), the cooling-heating mechanism (Peterson and Fabian, 2006; Zhuravleva et al., 2014) and formation of large scale structure (Borgani, 1995; Radburn-Smith et al., 2006; Feretti et al., 2012; Tugay and Voytsehovsky, 2017; Chakraborty et al., 2018). Temperature profiles of ICM in many clusters show a temperature drop towards the cluster core, the so-called cool-core clusters (Molendi and Pizzolato, 2001). Radiative cooling time scales in such clusters are significantly shorter than the Hubble time (Edge et al., 1992; White et al., 1997; Allen, 2000). In principle, this should lead to a slow infall of ICM towards the cluster core, the scenario known as cooling flow (Fabian, 1994). Peterson et al. (2003) found a large deficiency in the observed emission from low-temperature X-ray gas, in contrast to the prediction of the standard cooling-flow model.

There are many theories to account for this lack of cool X-ray emission. Feedback by Active Galactic Nucleus (AGN) is the most plausible theory to explain the suppression of cooling in the core (McNamara and Nulsen, 2007). Deep *Chandra* observations provide evidence in favor of AGN feedback through the exchange of mechanical energy between radio-emitting jets and the ICM (Fabian, 2012). This scenario is backed up by simulations (Dubois et al., 2010; Li and Bryan, 2012). Perseus is the brightest X-ray cluster ($z = 0.01756$), and the prototypical cool-core cluster. Ariel 5 observations of the Fe XXV and Fe XXVI emission features near 7 keV in Perseus established that its X-ray emission comes from a diffuse hot plasma, permeating the cluster volume (Mitchell et al., 1976). Later, the Fe XXV complex was detected with XMM-Newton at 6.7 keV, and it was used to investigate for the evidence of gas motions in Perseus core (Churazov et al., 2003, 2004).

Tremendous advancement in X-ray astronomy was made with the launch of the *Hitomi* Observatory on February 17, 2016. The Soft X-ray Spectrometer (SXS) (Kelley et al., 2016) on board *Hitomi* is equipped with an X-ray micro-calorimeter paired with a Soft X-ray Telescope (SXT). The micro-calorimeter spectrometer provided a resolving power of $R \sim 1250$ (Hitomi Collaboration et al., 2016), allowing the detection of many weak emission/absorption lines. The previously detected Fe XXV complex in Perseus was resolved by SXS into four main components – the resonance (w), intercombination (x,y), and forbidden (z) lines (see Table 3.1). Also, bulk and turbulent motions of the ICM were precisely measured for the first time with the SXS from Doppler shifts and broadening of spectral lines (Hitomi Collaboration et al., 2016).

Future X-ray missions like *XRISM* (follow-up of *Hitomi*) and *Athena* will offer a

plethora of high spectral resolution X-ray data. Complete computational plasma simulations are required to model several important cluster properties like temperature, turbulence, and metal abundances with high precision. In this paper, we present a study of the Fe XXV X-ray emission in Perseus based on *Hitomi* data with the spectral synthesis code CLOUDY (last reviewed by Ferland et al., 2017). This is a step towards achieving a precise spectral synthesis model for the above future X-ray missions.

With the advancement in spectral resolution, radiative transfer effects that are known in the optical will become accessible to X-ray astronomy. For example, in addition to optically thin line emission propagation (Case A), optically thick emission (Case B) is expected at sufficiently high column densities (Baker and Menzel, 1938). This is the theme of this paper. Similar effects in the presence of a continuous radiation source (Case C, Baker et al., 1938; Ferland, 1999) will be explored in a future paper.

The Case A/B/C transition is a property of all one- and two-electron systems, although most studies consider H and He in the optical because historically ground-based instruments had the highest throughputs and were able to obtain the highest resolution and S/N spectra. Only now, such works are becoming possible in the X-ray emitting gas from galaxy clusters. Previous works on X-ray one-electron Case A&B include Storey and Hummer (1995) and, for two-electron systems, Porter and Ferland (2007). In this work, we use CLOUDY to simulate the environment in the outer region of the Perseus core, showing Case A to B transition in the Fe XXV and Fe XXVI emission lines. Varying the column density of the simulated cloud is what drives this transition. Surprisingly, we observe Case A to B transition in both allowed and forbidden lines in the two-electron iron.

In addition to the Case A to B transfer, another important factor contributing to the change in the emission line intensities is the loss of identity of a line photon due to line interlocking. As a result of line interlocking, a Fe XXV line photon can be absorbed by Fe²³⁺, leading to autoionization in some fraction of the absorbing ion, ultimately destroying the Fe XXV K α photon by Resonant Auger Destruction (Band et al., 1990; Ross et al., 1996; Liedahl, 2005; Chakraborty et al., 2020d). Another atomic process, which we call Electron Scattering Escape (ESE), leads to the change in the Fe XXV K α line intensities at hydrogen column densities greater than 10²³ cm⁻². These two processes have been discussed in the previous Chapter, also in paper I (Chakraborty et al., 2020d). However, it is difficult to study these processes separately when explaining the variation of the Fe XXV K α line intensities with column density. The prime focus of this Chapter is on Case A to B transfer, with occasional references to line interlocking and RAD.

The organization of this paper is as follows. Section 3.2 summarizes all the relevant atomic processes. Section 3.3 discusses Case A to Case B transition for hydrogen and heavier elements. Section 3.4 presents our X-ray analysis of the *Hitomi* observational data. Section 3.5 discusses the parameters used for our simulations with CLOUDY. Section 4.4 demonstrates our results: optically thin (Case A) to optically thick (Case B) transition in Fe XXV and Fe XXVI, constraints on column density, the interplay between column density and metallicity, and effect of turbulence in Perseus core from

Table 3.1: List of energies and transition probabilities for the relevant $n=2,3$ to $n=1,2$ transitions in Fe XXV. $n=2$ levels are j -resolved in triplet P.

Label	Transition	Types	Energy (keV)	Transition Probability		
				CLOUDY	NIST	Difference
w	$2^1P \rightarrow 1^1S$	E_1	6.7007	4.54e+14	4.57e+14	1%
x	$2^3P_2 \rightarrow 1^1S$	M_2	6.6824	6.30e+09	6.64e+09	5%
y	$2^3P_1 \rightarrow 1^1S$	E_1+M_1	6.6679	4.11e+13	4.42e+13	8%
z	$2^3S \rightarrow 1^1S$	M_1	6.6368	2.15e+08	2.12e+08	1%
-	$3^1P \rightarrow 1^1S$	E_1	7.8758	1.29e+14	1.24e+14	4%
-	$3^3P_1 \rightarrow 1^1S$	E_1+M_1	7.8688	1.86e+13	1.50e+13	19%
-	$3^3P \rightarrow 2^3S$	E_1	1.2352	8.66e+12	8.08e+12	7%

the Fe XXV line ratios. Finally, we discuss our results in Section 3.7. Unless otherwise mentioned, all uncertainties in this paper are reported at 3σ intervals.

3.2 Atomic Processes

In this Section, we describe the various atomic data sources we apply in our spectral modelling. Some data sources, especially collisions, are uncertain and we try to estimate this, and show their effects on the spectrum.

3.2.1 Energy Levels

Helium energy levels are taken from Martin and Wiese (2006). Energy levels for heavier He-like ions, lithium through zinc, are taken from the CHIANTI atomic database version 5 (Landi et al., 2005; Dere et al., 1997).

We use j -resolved levels for the 2^3P terms in order to calculate accurate populations for these levels, and emissivities for the intercombination lines between them and the ground state. We include nls resolved levels for $n \leq 5$ (where n is the principal quantum number), while levels in the range $5 \leq n \leq 100$ are collapsed (see figure 1 in Ferland et al. (2013) for a schematic representation of resolved and collapsed levels). Energy levels of He-like ions are represented in Figure 3.1. In Table 3.1, there is a list of transition energies from $n = 2, 3 \rightarrow n = 1$ for Fe XXV in the interval of 6.5-8.0 keV.

3.2.2 Radiative transition rates

Porter and Ferland (2007) list all the sources of $n = 2, 3$ to $n = 2, 1$ transition probabilities used in CLOUDY. We show the dependence of transition probabilities for $2^1P \rightarrow 1^1S$, $2^3P \rightarrow 1^1S$, $2^3S \rightarrow 1^1S$, $3^1P \rightarrow 1^1S$, and $3^3P \rightarrow 1^1S$ transitions on atomic number (Z) in Figure 3.3. The significance of this Figure will be discussed in Section 3.3.3.

Figure 3.1: Grotrian diagram (not to scale) for He-like ions ($Z \geq 10$). Note that the relative order of the energy levels is different at lower ionic charges. x, y, z, and w transitions are marked with blue, green, purple, and red, respectively.

Table 3.1 gives a comparison between transition probabilities from CLOUDY and NIST¹ (version 5.6.1: Kramida et al., 2018). They show an agreement within 8% for $n = 2$ to $n = 1$ transitions, but a variation up to 19% for $n = 3$ to $n = 1$ transitions.

3.2.3 Recombination rate coefficients

Coefficients for radiative recombination (RR) rates are calculated from photoionization cross-sections using the Milne relation (Osterbrock and Ferland, 2006). Photoionization cross-sections for the ground state of He-like ions are taken from Verner et al. (1996), which uses analytic fits from the Opacity Project. Dielectronic recombination (DR) data are interpolated from Badnell (2006). See Porter and Ferland (2007), Ferland et al. (2013), Ferland et al. (2017) for a discussion on state-specific recombination rates.

3.2.4 Collisional data

Electron impact n -changing collisions

We interpolate the collision strengths from various atomic datasets for the right temperature (see Section 4.4) for $n = 2 - 5 \rightarrow 1$ transitions of Fe^{24+} . For higher n and Rydberg levels, we use the *ab initio* Born approximation theory by Lebedev and Beigman (1998), following the analysis in Guzmán et al. (2019).

¹<https://physics.nist.gov/asd>

Electron impact bound-free collisions

We take collisional ionization rate coefficients from Voronov (1997) for the ground state. For excited states, rate coefficients are taken from the hydrogenic routines of Allen (1973) for the lower temperatures, and from Sampson and Zhang (1988) at the high-temperature end.

3.3 The Case A & B framework in atoms and highly charged ions

3.3.1 Introduction to Case A & B, H I optical emission

Case A and Case B have been defined for hydrogen emission (Baker and Menzel, 1938; Osterbrock, 1989). Case A refers to an optically thin plasma where Lyman radiation is transmitted without absorption (Osterbrock and Ferland, 2006). At low hydrogen column density, all line photons emitted escape the cloud.

Case B occurs when the ionized cloud becomes optically thick to the H I Lyman resonance lines, due to high hydrogen column density. The Lyman photons undergo multiple scatterings and are degraded to lower energy photons (page 70-71, Osterbrock and Ferland, 2006). For instance, after approximately nine scatterings, a $\text{Ly}\beta$ photon gets degraded to a $\text{H}\alpha$ photon plus two-photon continuum. Line formation in most nebulae can be explained by conditions closer to Case B. In this limit, the electron density must be small enough ($n_e \leq 10^8 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) for collisional deexcitation rate to be lower than spontaneous emissions (Hummer and Storey, 1987).

3.3.2 Atomic Helium

Radiative lifetimes for excited helium atoms range between less than a nanosecond to several minutes. For example, 2^1P_1 decays to the ground state in 0.56 ns, which is very short compared to the decay times in 2^3P_2 (3.05 s) and the metastable 2^3S levels (131 minutes). These are respectively examples of E_1 (electric dipole), M_2 (magnetic quadrupole), and M_1 (magnetic dipole) transitions for $n = 2 \rightarrow 1$. The decay of 2^3P_1 to the ground state has a radiative lifetime of ~ 5.68 ms and is a combination of E_1 and M_1 .

In Figure 3.3 we plot transition probabilities for He-like ions with $2 \leq Z \leq 30$. From the Figure it is clear that in helium, there is no fast transition to the ground from excited triplet states due to their longer radiative lifetimes (and smaller transition probabilities ($A_{u,l}$)). Optical thickness is proportional to the absorption cross-section at frequency ν (α_ν), which is proportional to $A_{u,l}$ (refer to equation 6.3 and 3.3). Therefore, for helium, there will be no Case A (optically thin) to Case B (optically thick) transition for triplet to ground transitions. Fast transitions only occur in the allowed singlet to singlet transitions (E_1) with decay times of the order of nanoseconds and large absorption cross-sections, thus allowing for Case A to B transitions. This is not the case, however, for higher atomic numbers. Atomic number dependence of transition probability for allowed and forbidden transitions will be discussed in Section 3.3.3.

3.3.3 X-ray emission from He-like Fe XXV

Along the two-electron iso-sequence, the next abundant elements are C, O, and N, emitted in soft X-rays and discussed by Porter and Ferland (2007). This paper continues to iron, inspired by recent *Hitomi* observations of the Fe K α complex in the Perseus galaxy cluster.

In Fe XXV, in contrast to the atomic helium discussed in Section 3.3.2, triplet to singlet transitions can also become optically thick (Case B) along with the singlet to singlet transitions. This is surprising at first sight, but can be explained with the transition probability (A_{ki}) dependence on the atomic number (Z) for different types of transitions.

Probabilities for E₁ transitions ($2\ ^1P-1\ ^1S$ (w), $3\ ^1P-1\ ^1S$) grow with the fourth power of Z ($A_{ki} \propto Z^4$, Johnson et al., 2002), whereas transition probabilities for M₁ ($2\ ^3S-1\ ^1S$ (z)) and M₂ ($2\ ^3P_2-1\ ^1S$ (x)) grow much faster with Z ((approximately $\propto Z^{10}$ and $\propto Z^8$, Lin et al., 1977)). The transition probabilities for $2\ ^3P_1-1\ ^1S$ (y) and $3\ ^3P_1-1\ ^1S$ are a combination of E1 and M1, and also grow much faster than the allowed E₁ transitions. Therefore in higher Z ions like iron, transition probabilities ($A_{u,l}$) and optical depths for some of the triplet to singlet transitions become comparable to that of the allowed singlet to singlet transitions (see Figure 3.3). This implies that Case A to B transition occurs in singlet to singlet as well as triplet to triplet transitions in Fe XXV and other higher Z He-like ions.

3.3.4 X-ray emission from H-like Fe XXVI

Unlike helium, there is no fundamental difference between atomic hydrogen and the highly charged H-like ions. This point is elaborated in Section 3.6.1.

Figure 3.2: The outer region of Perseus core from Hitomi SXS observation (marked with Obs23 : out) overlaid on a *Chandra* X-ray image of Perseus.

Figure 3.3: Left: Transition probabilities vs. Z for certain $n=2$ to $n=1$ transitions for He-like ions. Right: Transition probabilities vs. Z for certain $n=3$ to $n=1$ transitions.

Figure 3.4: The black solid line shows the best-fitting model with x , y , z , w emissivities set to zero, and four added Gaussians centered at their redshifted laboratory energies. Red, blue, green, purple dotted lines show the four Gaussians for w , x , y , and z separately. The black dotted line shows the `bvvapec` model without x , y , z , and w .

3.4 Line ratios from *Hitomi* observations

The observational spectra for the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ is extracted using HEASoft version 6.25² in the outer region of Perseus core following the *Hitomi* step by step analysis guide³. We use the following observations with observation IDs: 100040020, 100040030, 100040040, and 100040050 for extracting the spectra for the region marked with Obs23:out in Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018b) (we show this region in Figure 3.2). Event files for these observations are combined and filtered with the Xselect package. Four NXB spectra are extracted separately for the four event files with `sxsnxbgen`, and averaged using `mathpha`. RMF, exposure map, and ARF were generated using `sxsmkrmf`, `ahexpmap`, and `aharfgen` respectively. For fitting the spectra, we use Xspec version 12.10.1 (Arnaud, 1996).

The X-ray emission from our region of interest was modeled as a velocity broadened single-temperature collisionally ionized plasma with variable element abundances (`bvvapec`), attenuated by the cold matter absorption in our Galaxy (`TBabs`). The absorbing hydrogen column density was set to $1.38 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (Leiden/Argentine/Bonn Survey of Galactic HI: Kalberla et al. (2005)) The `bvvapec` model was modified whenever necessary by setting the emissivities to zero for selected lines, following the addition of corresponding Gaussian components. The contamination by the central AGN emission is negligible in the outer region; thus such effects were not included in our model.

We use the outer region temperature ($4.05 \pm 0.01 \text{ keV}$), Fe abundance (0.65 ± 0.01), and turbulent velocity ($141 \pm 5 \text{ km/s}$) from a broad-band fit in the energy range 1.8-20.0 keV from Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018b) (errors are reported at 1σ confidence level). Solar abundance table by Lodders and Palme (2009) was used throughout. For calculating the line fluxes for x, y, z, and w, we set the line emissivities for these lines to zero, and add four Gaussians with energies centered at their redshifted laboratory energies ($E_{0x} = 6.68245 \text{ keV}$, $E_{0y} = 6.66790 \text{ keV}$, $E_{0z} = 6.63684 \text{ keV}$, $E_{0w} = 6.70076 \text{ keV}$). In the modified `bvvapec` model: `tbabs*(bvvapec + zgaussx + zgaussy + zgaussz + zgaussw)`, we tie the line widths of x, y, z together, and set the line width for w free to vary. This is because w is reported to be slightly broader than the other three lines in Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex (Hitomi Collaboration et al., 2018b). Normalization of the four Gaussians were set free, and redshifts were tied together. Our best-fit model for the observed spectra for Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex from Obs23:out is shown in Figure 3.4 with a black solid line. Red, blue, green, and purple dotted lines show the four Gaussians for w, x, y, and z, respectively. The black dotted line shows the `bvvapec` model with x, y, z, and w emissivities set to zero. In such conditions, major contributions to the `bvvapec` model come from Fe XXIV satellite lines, following the contributions from Cr XXIII, and Fe XXIII in the energy range of the Figure. Best-fit redshift for our model is $z = 0.0173308^{+2.53e-05}_{-2.46e-05}$. Best-fit parameters for the four Gaussians and line fluxes with the line ratios are listed in Tables 3.2 and 3.3, respectively.

²<https://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/docs/software/heasoft/>

³https://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/docs/hitomi/analysis/hitomi_analysis_guide_20160624.pdf

Table 3.2: Best-fit normalization and sigma of the four Gaussians from our model: $\text{tbabs}^*(\text{bvvapec} + \text{zgauss}_x + \text{zgauss}_y + \text{zgauss}_z + \text{zgauss}_w)$. Temperature, Fe abundance, and turbulent velocity in the bvvapec model are set to the values from broad-band fits in Obs23:out. Line emissivities of x, y, z, and w are set to zero.

Label	Normalization ($\times 10^{-5}$ photons/cm $^{-2}$ /s)	Sigma (keV)
x	$9.80^{+0.92}_{-0.88}$	$3.61\text{e-}03^{+2.78\text{e-}04}_{-2.63\text{e-}04}$
y	$10.56^{+1.03}_{-0.98}$	$3.61\text{e-}03^{+2.78\text{e-}04}_{-2.63\text{e-}04}$
z	$15.34^{+1.10}_{-1.07}$	$3.61\text{e-}03^{+2.78\text{e-}04}_{-2.63\text{e-}04}$
w	$39.22^{+1.56}_{-1.52}$	$4.17\text{e-}03^{+1.94\text{e-}04}_{-1.87\text{e-}04}$

Table 3.3: List of net line fluxes and ratios with w for the lines in Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex from the best-fit model. Line fluxes and their errors are reported in units of erg cm $^{-2}$ s $^{-1}$.

Label	Line flux	Ratio with w
x	$1.01\text{e-}12^{+9.46\text{e-}14}_{-9.14\text{e-}14}$	$0.249^{+0.025}_{-0.025}$
y	$1.09\text{e-}12^{+1.08\text{e-}13}_{-9.98\text{e-}14}$	$0.268^{+0.029}_{-0.026}$
z	$1.57\text{e-}12^{+1.13\text{e-}13}_{-1.09\text{e-}13}$	$0.387^{+0.031}_{-0.031}$
w	$4.06\text{e-}12^{+1.61\text{e-}13}_{-1.58\text{e-}13}$	-

3.5 Simulation Parameters

For the CLOUDY calculations, we simulate the environment in the outer region of Perseus core, introduced as Obs23:out in Section 3.4. We choose the temperature inside the error interval of the observation: $4.05^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$ keV. The hydrogen density is set at 0.03 cm^{-3} . Note that, the hydrogen density drops with increasing distance from the cluster core. For simplicity, we assume an average hydrogen density of 0.03 cm^{-3} for our region of interest (30-60 kpc). The radial dependence of hydrogen density will be explored in future papers.

We set the Fe abundance to be in the range of $0.65^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$ of solar, as discussed in Section 3.4. Section 3.6.4, where we show the variation of line ratios with changing metallicity, is an exception. We use the solar abundance table provided by Lodders and Palme (2009) to match with Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018b). The turbulence is set to 150 km/s (this choice is elaborated later in Section 3.6.3) for all our calculations except for Section 3.6.3, where we use two additional values for turbulence. In Section 3.6.3 and partly in Section 3.6.4, hydrogen column density is fixed at the reported value by Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018a) ($N_{\text{H,hot}} \sim 1.88 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). This is the column density of hot absorbing gas, derived from a best-fit baseline model defined with SPEX (Kaastra et al., 1996). In their model $N_{\text{H,hot}}$ is set as a free parameter, along with temperature and turbulent velocity of hot gas, emission measure, redshift, and abundances of Si, S, Ar, Ca, Cr, Mn, Fe, and Ni.

For the collision strengths, we use the recent calculations of Si et al. (2017), who adopted the independent process and isolated resonances approximation using distorted waves (IPIRDW). Since we find instances of disagreement between observed and calculated line ratios, we also check the effect of different atomic datasets on the calculated line ratios (such as Figure 4.5 and Figure 3.13). These include collision data from Whiteford et al. (2001), A. D. Whiteford (2005)⁴, and A. Giunta (2012)⁵. Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018b) shows the presence of resonance scattering (RS) in Perseus core, which results in flux suppression in w. In the outer region (Obs23:out), the flux suppression factor in w is reported to be ~ 1.28 . We make a correction for this factor for our calculations, as we use a simple model with plane-parallel geometry that does not account for the photons lost due to resonance scattering in our line of sight. This will be further discussed in Section 3.7.

3.6 Results

3.6.1 Case A & Case B in Iron

Fe XXV

The Case A to B transition happens when the total line-center optical depth of the Lyman lines becomes ≥ 1 . Note that the variation in optical depth is determined by the column density of that species, Fe XXV, in this case. The column density of Fe²⁴⁺ ($N(\text{Fe}^{24+})$) can be calculated from the hydrogen column density ($N(\text{H})$) for a given metal abundance (Fe/H), and ionization fraction ($\text{Fe}^{24+}/\text{Fe}$) with the following equation:

$$N(\text{Fe}^{24+}) = \left(\frac{\text{Fe}^{24+}}{\text{Fe}} \right) \left(\frac{\text{Fe}}{\text{H}} \right) N(\text{H}) \quad (3.1)$$

This conversion is shown in the top x-axes in Figure 3.6, 3.7, and 3.8.

Decay rates in Fe²⁴⁺ for triplet to singlet and singlet to singlet transitions are comparable to each other for some transitions, as discussed in Section 3.3.3. This allows the transfer from the optically thin (Case A) to the optically thick regimes (Case B) for singlet to singlet, as well as triplet to singlet transitions.

Figure 3.5 (refer to Figure 2.3 in Chapter 2) shows the line intensities for x, y, z, and w in the Fe XXV K α complex. The continuous increase in the line intensities with column density makes it difficult to detect where the Case A to B transition occurs for the individual spectral lines. To demonstrate the Case A to B transition, it is best to consider the variation of line ratios with column density. Among the four members in Fe XXV K α complex, w is the first line to become optically thick, followed by y, x, and z (Refer to Figure 2.1b in Chapter 2). z only becomes optically thick at very high column densities ($N_{\text{H}} \geq 10^{25} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). The Figure also gives an estimate of what fraction of the optical depth for the four lines comes from their single-line optical depth solely (in this case absorption by Fe²⁴⁺ only). The total

⁴ADF04, OPEN-ADAS database, helike_adw05#fe24.dat, Website: <https://open.adas.ac.uk/>

⁵ADF04, ls#fe24.dat, OPEN-ADAS database

Figure 3.5: Absolute line intensities of x, y, z, and w vs. log of hydrogen column density.

line-center optical depths in x, y, z, and w respectively have $\leq 1\%$, $\sim 60\%$, $\leq 1\%$, and $\sim 100\%$ contribution from absorption by Fe^{24+} . As z is the last line to become optically thick, we plot line ratios of x, y, and w relative to z with hydrogen column density (see Figure 3.6).

In the lower column densities, the lines ratios are parallel to each other and remain constant with increasing column density. This is because the individual line intensities are all parallelly increasing when the column density, and therefore optical depth, is small (Case A).

At higher column densities (Case B limit), the Figure shows an overall decrease in w/z , x/z , and y/z , which can be caused by the decrease in the numerator, or increase in the denominator, or a combination of these two. In-between these two cases, there is a transition region representing the transfer from Case A to Case B.

The probability that an x photon gets absorbed by Fe^{24+} itself is $\leq 1\%$. The effect of Case A to B transfer in x following absorption by Fe^{24+} is, therefore, very minimal. Apart from this, contributions from RAD and ESE cause a deficit in the x line intensity (paper I).

Unlike x, total line-center optical depth in y has a $\sim 60\%$ contribution from absorption by Fe^{24+} itself. When a y photon gets absorbed by Fe^{24+} , it leads to two possible modes of re-emission. It can either be re-emitted as a y photon or make a transition to $2\ ^3S$ following the emission of a z photon. The probability of re-emission via either of these modes depends on the transition probabilities between the levels or, more specifically, branching ratios. The branching ratio for scattered y photon being re-emitted as a $2\ ^3P_1 \rightarrow 2\ ^3S$ following a z transition is quite small :

$$\frac{A_{2\ ^3P_1 \rightarrow 2\ ^3S}}{(A_{2\ ^3P_1 \rightarrow 2\ ^3S} + A_{2\ ^3P_1 \rightarrow 1\ ^1S})} \sim 10^{-5}$$

Therefore the majority of the scattered y photons will be re-emitted as y with no

Figure 3.6: Fe XXV line ratios with respect to z for $2 \rightarrow 1$ transitions vs log of hydrogen column density. The x-axis on top shows log of Fe^{24+} column density.

decrease in y intensity. This indicates a possible increase in z intensity, causing the slower drop of y/z ratio with increasing column density in Figure 3.6.

Similarly, $\sim 100\%$ of w photons are scattered by Fe^{24+} . Upon being scattered, there are two possible modes of re-emission for w photons. The branching ratio for $2^1P \rightarrow 2^1S$ following the transition to the ground is very small:

$$\frac{A_{2^1P \rightarrow 2^1S}}{(A_{2^1P \rightarrow 2^1S} + A_{2^1P \rightarrow 1^1S})} \sim 10^{-6}$$

Therefore almost all the scattered w photons will be re-emitted as w . The drop in the w/z ratio in Figure 3.6 mostly results from an increase in z intensity apart from the resonance scattering effects in w at large column densities.

Even though none of the $n = 2 \rightarrow 1$ photon takes part in the Case A to B transfer, higher n Lyman lines ($n = 3, 4, 5 \dots \rightarrow 1$) show such transfer. The factor contributing to the increase in z is Case A to B transfer in $n = 3, 4, 5 \dots \rightarrow 1$ photons. In an optically thick cloud, these photons are scattered, followed by emission of Balmer line photons plus the $n = 2 \rightarrow 1$ photons. This results in a surplus of $n = 2 \rightarrow 1$ photons. Tables 4.1 and 4.2 in Osterbrock and Ferland (2006) show the Case A and Case B limit in HI recombination lines. Here we discuss the increase in z intensity due to this process, whereas the slight increase in y intensity will be discussed in Section 3.6.2.

Case A to B transfer for $3^3P \rightarrow 1^1S$ transition is shown in the upper panel of Figure 3.7. Lower panel shows Case A to B transition in $n = 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 \rightarrow 1$ photons. A plot similar to that of 1b in paper I is shown in Figure 3.8 comparing the single line and total line-center optical depths for $3^3P \rightarrow 1^1S$ transition. Line ratios in Figure 3.7 are taken relative to z for the reason explained previously.

Figure 3.7: Upper panel: Fe XXV line ratios with respect to z for $3^3P \rightarrow 1^1S$ transition vs. log of hydrogen column density. Lower panel: Fe XXV line ratios with respect to z for $n = 4, 5, \dots \rightarrow 1^1S$ transitions vs. log of hydrogen column density. The x-axis on top shows log of Fe^{24+} column density.

Once a photon for $3^3P \rightarrow 1^1S$ transition gets scattered, the probability that it will emit a $3^3P \rightarrow 2^3S$ following the emission of a $2^3S \rightarrow 1^1S$ (z) photon is $\sim 32\%$ in one scattering:

$$\frac{A_{3^3P \rightarrow 2^3S}}{(A_{3^3P \rightarrow 2^3S} + A_{3^3P \rightarrow 1^1S})} \sim 0.32$$

Therefore, for a single event of scattering, $3^3P \rightarrow 1^1S$ photons have a 32% probability of being converted to z and Balmer series line photons. At a hydrogen column density of $N_H = 10^{25} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, the triplet to singlet transition photons will experience multiple scatterings because of their large optical depths (~ 100 , see Figure 3.8). The majority of these line photons will be converted to z and Balmer series photons at this column density. This contributes to the increase in the intensity of z

Figure 3.8: Optical depth vs. hydrogen column density for $3\ ^3P \rightarrow 1\ ^1S$ transition in Fe XXV. Solid: Total line-center optical depth, Dotted: Individual line optical depth. The x-axis on top shows log of Fe^{24+} column density. The blue dashed line marks the optical depth of unity.

line photons in Figure 3.6, and a decrease in the intensity of $3\ ^3P \rightarrow 1\ ^1S$ line photons in the top panel of Figure 3.7. Likewise, $n = 4, 5 \dots 10 \rightarrow 1$ transition line photons show a similar behavior indicating a Case A to B transfer (bottom panel of Figure 3.7), and selectively contribute to the increase in z intensity. Although we show the Case A to B transfer of Lyman line photons up to $n=10$, we include collapsed levels up to $n \leq 100$ in our simulation. The net increase in the z line intensity will result from the collective Case A to B transfer of Lyman line photons for transitions from all the levels up to $n=100$.

Fe XXVI

As mentioned in Section 3.3.4, there is no fundamental difference between Fe^{25+} and other hydrogenic ions. We show the Case A to B transition for the line intensity ratios $\text{Ly}\beta$, $\text{Ly}\gamma$, $\text{H}\alpha$, and $\text{H}\beta$ with respect to $\text{Ly}\alpha$ in Figure 3.9 ($\text{Ly}\alpha$, $\text{Ly}\beta$, $\text{Ly}\gamma$, $\text{H}\alpha$, and $\text{H}\beta$ are $n=2 \rightarrow 1$, $n=3 \rightarrow 1$, $n=4 \rightarrow 1$, $n=3 \rightarrow 2$, and $n=4 \rightarrow 2$ transitions with wavelengths $1.781\,77\ \text{\AA}$, $1.503\,37\ \text{\AA}$, $1.425\,41\ \text{\AA}$, $9.621\,54\ \text{\AA}$, and $7.127\,06\ \text{\AA}$, respectively). The bottom and top axes in the Figure respectively show the hydrogen and Fe^{25+} column densities. Line ratios are plotted instead of the individual line intensities for the same reason, as discussed in Section 3.6.1.

Figure 3.9 shows that line ratios remain unchanged at small column densities when the lines are optically thin (Case A). But at higher column densities, the cloud becomes optically thick, the spectrum goes to Case B, and the higher n Lyman lines like $\text{Ly}\beta$ and $\text{Ly}\gamma$ degrade to $\text{H}\alpha$, and $\text{H}\beta$ respectively. This causes the Lyman lines

Figure 3.9: Fe XXVI line intensity ratios with respect to $\text{Ly}\alpha$ vs. log of hydrogen column density. The x-axis on top shows log of Fe^{25+} column density. The dashed line is the integrated two-photon continuum relative to $\text{Ly}\alpha$.

to become weaker, and the Balmer lines to become stronger. Such analysis can be extended to other hydrogenic ions like Si XIV, S XVI, Ar XVIII, and Ca XX for constraining/measuring column density. This will be explored in future papers.

3.6.2 Constraints on Column density

We run a line ratio diagnostic for Fe XXV $\text{K}\alpha$ complex with column density using the Case A to B transition. Here we plot the variation of Fe XXV line ratios (RS corrected) relative to the strongest resonance (w) line with increasing hydrogen column density in Figure 3.10.

At lower column densities, line ratios remain constant with the increase in column density. Apart from the RS effects at the higher column densities, line intensities in w increase linearly, while z and x increase faster and slower than linear, respectively. The behavior of x line intensity with column density is discussed in Chapter 2. Faster than linear growth in z is due to the Case A to B transfer in selective $n = 3, 4 \dots \rightarrow 1$ photons (See section 3.6.1).

Similar to the increase in z/w , the slight increase in y/w in the high column density can also be explained with Case A to B transfer in $n = 3, 4 \dots \rightarrow 1$ line photons to generate Balmer line photons plus the $n = 2 \rightarrow 1$ transition photons. Such transition makes all the $n = 2 \rightarrow 1$ transitions brighter in the Case B limit compared to Case A. This process strengthens the weak $n = 2 \rightarrow 1$ transitions more than w, the strongest, leading to the slight rise in y/w at the high-column-density limit.

The top panel of Figure 3.10 shows the variation of line ratios relative to w with hydrogen column density for different collision datasets. The bottom panel of the Figure compares the variation in line ratios calculated with CLOUDY, with

Figure 3.10: Variation of x/w , y/w , and z/w line ratios with hydrogen column density. Top panel: Line ratios calculated with CLOUDY for different collision datasets; Bottom panel: Line ratios calculated with CLOUDY with their net uncertainties overplotted with the *Hitomi* observed line ratios. Solid vertical lines show constraints on column density. *Hitomi* reported hydrogen column density is shown with black dashed lines in each panel.

the observed line ratios to get constraint on column density. The shaded horizontal regions are the observed line ratios with their uncertainties at the reported column density by Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018a). Section 3.4 describes the extraction of line ratios along with their errors from the observed spectra. The regions between the two solid lines in all three panels enclose the calculated line ratios with CLOUDY. The enclosed regions are inclusive of the uncertainty in temperature and collision strengths coming from different collision datasets. Refer to Table 3.4 for the uncertainties in collision datasets.

The intersection regions between observed and calculated line ratios for x/w and z/w predict a hydrogen column density of $N_{\text{H}} \leq 2.95 \times 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, and $N_{\text{H}} \leq 2.75 \times 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively. The solid vertical lines in the bottom panel of Figure 4.5 show the upper limit of column density from these two ratios. The y/w ratio calculated with CLOUDY intersect with the observed value for all column densities below 10^{25} cm^{-2} . These upper limits calculated from x/w , y/w , and z/w ratios are all consistent with the reported hydrogen column density $N_{\text{H,hot}} \sim 1.88 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (shown with the black vertical dashed lines) for Perseus.

3.6.3 Effects of turbulence

In Figure 3.11, we show the effect of turbulence on the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex line ratios. Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018b) found a difference in turbulent broadening between w (159–167 km/s), and x , y , z (136–150 km/s) in region Obs23:out. We use a turbulent velocity of 150 km/s for simplicity in our simulation of the outer region of Perseus core. Figure 3.11 shows that such a quiescent gas environment barely affects the line ratios, as the difference in the line ratios calculated at the turbulence 0 km/s and 150 km/s is very small.

Figure 3.11: Line intensity ratio relative to w vs. log of hydrogen column density. Solid: no turbulence, Dashed: Turbulence 150 km/s, Dotted: Turbulence 500 km/s.

We also plot the line ratios at the turbulence of 500 km/s. Such a high value of the turbulence is not applicable in our region of interest, but may apply for gas in

Figure 3.12: Left, middle and right panels show x/w , y/w , and z/w as a function of hydrogen column density and metallicity, respectively.

Figure 3.13: Line intensity ratios versus metallicity at $N_{\text{H}} = 1.88 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Blue, green, purple lines in left, middle, and right panels enclose the x/w , y/w , and z/w calculated with CLOUDY. The enclosed regions are inclusive of the uncertainty in temperature, and different collision datasets. Observed line ratios with errors are shown with the horizontal bars in all three panels.

other environments such as merging galaxy clusters (Cassano and Brunetti, 2005).

Optical depth can be expressed as a product of column density (N), and absorption cross-section (α_{ν}):

$$\tau_{\nu} = N\alpha_{\nu} \quad (3.2)$$

where α_{ν} is inversely proportional to the total Doppler velocity

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{\nu}(x) &= \frac{\lambda^3 g_u}{8\pi g_l} \frac{A_{u,l}}{\pi^{1/2} u_{\text{Dop}}} \varphi_{\nu}(x) \\ &= \frac{\pi^{1/2} q_e^2 \lambda f_{l,u}}{m_e c u_{\text{Dop}}} \varphi_{\nu}(x) [\text{cm}^2]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

Here $A_{u,l}$ is the downward transition probability, $f_{l,u}$ is the oscillator strength and other symbols have their usual meaning (Mihalas, 1970). If the temperature is held constant, an increase in the turbulent velocity decreases α_{ν} , which decreases the overall optical depth.

Thus, ideally, to achieve the same optical depth at zero and higher turbulent velocity, a higher column density should be required for the latter case. However, this outcome gets reversed due to line interlocking of x, y, and z with other ions (e.g., Fe^{23+} , Cr^{22+} , and Fe^{22+} ; see Chapter 2). The higher the turbulent velocity is, the higher the Doppler width of a line and the more pronounced the line interlocking effects will be. Total line-center optical depth will, therefore, increase with turbulent velocity rather than decrease, as equation 3.3 suggests.

3.6.4 Interplay between column density and metallicity

Figure 3.12 shows the line ratios relative to w as contour plots by varying the hydrogen column density and metallicity. In the low-column-density limit, the line ratios are minimally affected by change in metallicity. Figure 3.13 shows the effects

Figure 3.14: The ratio of observed to CLOUDY predicted line ratios plotted as a function of observed line ratios. All the ratios are taken with respect to the resonance (w) line. The points with red, blue, and purple error bars show the degree of agreement with the *Hitomi* observed line ratios for x/w, y/w, and z/w, respectively. Vertical error bars are calculated using observational and CLOUDY estimated uncertainties. The blue dotted line shows the ideal situation where observed line ratios exactly match with the predicted.

Table 3.4: List of collision strengths at 4 keV from different atomic datasets for $n = 2 \rightarrow 1$ transitions in Fe XXV.

Label	Transition	Collision Strengths				Difference
		Whiteford +2001	Whiteford +2005	Giunta +2012	Si +2017	
w	$2^1P \rightarrow 1^1S$	3.97e-3	3.99e-3	4.32e-3	4.18e-3	8%
x	$2^3P_2 \rightarrow 1^1S$	7.27e-4	7.39e-4	6.72e-4	7.13e-4	9%
y	$2^3P_1 \rightarrow 1^1S$	7.24e-4	7.31e-4	8.68e-4	7.90e-4	17%
-	$2^3P_0 \rightarrow 1^1S$	1.48e-4	1.48e-4	1.35e-4	1.51e-4	11%
z	$2^3S \rightarrow 1^1S$	3.05e-4	4.28e-4	2.46e-4	3.16e-4	42%
-	$2^1S \rightarrow 1^1S$	8.41e-4	8.59e-4	8.68e-4	1.05e-3	20%

of metallicity on the line ratios at the reported value of hydrogen column density by Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018a) ($N_{\text{H,hot}} \sim 1.88 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). The uncertainties in temperature and collision strengths from the sources mentioned previously contribute to the uncertainties in the line ratios (shown with the solid enclosed lines in Figure 3.13). At the reported hydrogen column density, x, y, and z are optically thin (Chapter 2). Therefore, the line ratios are minimally affected with change in metallicity as these lines are still optically thin for the metallicity range ($0 \leq Z(\text{solar}) \leq 5$) shown in the Figure.

Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018b) use deprojected heavy element abundances relative to solar in the inner 150 kpc region from *Chandra* data archive for a spherically symmetric Perseus model. At a distance of 30 – 60 kpc from the central AGN of Perseus core, the reported range in metallicity is $\sim 0.5 - 0.75$ of solar. (see Figure 7 in their paper). We overplot the CLOUDY calculated line ratios with *Hitomi* observed line ratios, and obtain a region of overlap for all the metallicities between 0 and 5. This is consistent with the reported metallicity range for the outer region of Perseus core, but calculating/constraining the best-fit metallicity requires an extension of parameter space up to higher column densities.

In the high-column-density limit, the line ratios exhibit a clear variation with metallicity (see Figure 3.12). It can be seen that a smaller metallicity is equivalent to a larger hydrogen column density for the same optical depth. In systems with hydrogen column densities greater than 10^{23} cm^{-2} , like Seyfert 2 Galaxies (Risaliti et al., 1999; Terashima and Wilson, 2001; Mocz et al., 2011), such comparison between the calculated and observed line ratios can be used to measure/constrain metallicities.

3.7 Summary

New generations of micro-calorimeter on board *Hitomi* made precision spectroscopy in X-ray possible for the first time. This enables us to explore radiative transfer effects like Case A to B transition in X-ray, previously observed in optical / UV (Baker and Menzel, 1938). In this paper, we document the Case A to B transition for H-like and He-like iron and show that this can be used to constrain column density. We also show the effect of and turbulence, and interplay between column density and metallicity in the outer region of the Perseus core using a line ratio diagnostic. In addition, we show that highly charged He-like systems behave differently from He I and other low charge He-like systems. This is due to the atomic number dependence of transition probabilities, leading to fast transitions in non-allowed triplet to singlet transitions.

From a comparison between the CLOUDY predicted and *Hitomi* observed line ratios in the outer region of Perseus core for the observed temperature, column density, and metallicity (see Figure 3.14), we find an agreement of $\sim 91\%$, 99% , 98% in the x/w , y/w , and z/w ratios, but consistency within the errors.

In the case B limit, two factors contribute to the variation in line ratios with column density for the same sets of physical parameters. First, line photons get absorbed in the cloud and are re-emitted as different lines (see Section 3.6.1). Second, line photons are absorbed in the cloud and re-emitted in a different direction leading to the change in intensity of line photons along our line of sight (i.e., resonance scattering). Physically, it represents the migration of photons from the center of the cluster, where there is a photon deficit, to the outer regions, where there would be a photon surplus (Gilfanov et al., 1987). Our current model treats the cluster as a single sphere and can not recover this physics region wise. A proper model of the variation in density and temperature across the cluster will be investigated in a later paper. The first line to become optically thick is w (see Figure 1b in paper I). We use a flux suppression factor of ~ 1.28 for w reported by Hitomi Collaboration

et al. (2018b) at the outer region of Perseus core for the best-fit column density $N_{\text{H,hot}} \sim 1.88 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (Hitomi Collaboration et al., 2018a). Flux suppression in x, y, and z is insignificant at such small column density but needs to be considered for higher column densities when these lines become optically thick.

In Section 3.6.2, we introduced a novel method of measuring/constraining column density from Case A to B transition. In the case of Perseus, x, y, and z are still in the optically thin regime (Case A). Therefore, we only get an upper limit in column density instead of a specific value. However, this method will be useful in systems with higher column densities ($N_{\text{H}} \geq 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) in the optically thick regime (Case B) for measuring column density.

Chapter 4 Line formation under Case A, Case B, Case C, and Case D in H- and He-like iron for a photoionized cloud

4.1 Introduction

Microcalorimeter X-ray missions like *Hitomi* and the upcoming missions *XRISM* and *Athena* will provide unprecedented spectroscopic resolution. Soft X-ray Spectrometer (SXS, Kelley et al., 2016) onboard *Hitomi* (Hitomi Collaboration et al., 2016) resolved the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex in four components for the first time. A plethora of high-resolution X-ray data from these missions will be available within the next few decades. Interpreting these high-resolution spectra requires a clear understanding of the line formation processes in the X-ray emitting plasma.

Line formation in gaseous nebulae was first studied in the 1930s in a series of papers by Menzel (1937), Menzel and Baker (1937), Baker and Menzel (1938), and Baker et al. (1938) for the formation of optical HI lines. Two limiting cases were discussed- “Case A” and “Case B”. Case A occurs when the nebula is optically thin, and the line photons emitted by recombination escape the cloud freely. Case B occurs if the nebula is optically thick, and the line photons scatter multiple times in the cloud. Higher-order Lyman lines are converted into Balmer and $Ly\alpha$ (or $K\alpha$) photons or two-photon continuum. Note that in their study, the source of the radiation was assumed to be of stellar origin. Stars in the gaseous nebulae might have strong Lyman absorption lines in the Spectral Energy Distribution (SED), and there is almost no continuum pumping. This will be relevant to the discussion later.

A third case occurring in optically thin irradiated clouds, “Case C”, was introduced by Baker et al. (1938) and later followed up by Chamberlain (1953) and Ferland (1999). In Case C, lines escape the cloud freely like Case A. But unlike Case A, Case C spectrum is enhanced by continuum pumping.

Some recent studies (Luridiana et al., 2009; Peimbert et al., 2016) discussed a fourth case, ‘Case D’, which occurs in optically thick irradiated systems. Similar to Case B, line photons scatter multiple times in Case D before escaping the optically thick cloud. But unlike Case B, Case D spectrum is enhanced by continuum pumping.

Most of the previous works on Case A, B, C, and D, both theoretical and observational, were focused on the optical, ultraviolet, and infrared regime (Menzel, 1937; Menzel and Baker, 1937; Baker and Menzel, 1938; Baker et al., 1938; Chamberlain, 1953; Soifer et al., 1981; Malkan and Sargent, 1982; Hummer and Storey, 1987; Keel and Windhorst, 1991; Ferland, 1999; Sánchez et al., 2007; Stelzer et al., 2012; Mennickent et al., 2016; Peimbert et al., 2017), with a small number of studies on the X-rays - Storey and Hummer (1988) and Storey and Hummer (1995) for one-electron and Porter and Ferland (2007) for two-electron ions. Some other previous studies on soft X-ray spectrum are Paerels and Kahn (2003), Bianchi et al. (2005), Cappi et al. (2006), Guainazzi and Bianchi (2007), Mao et al. (2018). Note that, Kinkhabwala et al. (2002) outlined many of the physical processes discussed in this paper, focusing on second and third-row elements.

The purpose of our paper is to describe improvements to the widely disseminated code CLOUDY with simultaneous radiative transfer and ionization solutions. This paper presents diagnostic diagrams making it possible to measure column densities from line intensities. Here, we discuss the line formation processes for the four Menzel and Baker cases – Case A, B, C, and D for H-like and He-like iron in photoionized plasma. This will be essential for interpreting the future high-resolution microcalorimeter observations in the presence of a photoionizing source.

This Chapter is based on the third paper of the series “X-ray spectroscopy in the microcalorimeter era”, the first two papers of which discussed the atomic processes in a collisionally excited plasma. Chapter 2 and Chakraborty et al. (2020b) discussed line interlocking and Resonant Auger Destruction (Ross et al., 1978; Band et al., 1990; Ross et al., 1996; Liedahl, 2005), and electron scattering escape (ESE) in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. Chapter 3 and Chakraborty et al. (2020c) discussed Case A to B transition in H- and He- like iron. The present Chapter explores photoionized X-ray plasma with CLOUDY (Ferland et al., 2017) for a power-law SED. Note that, the results shown in all three papers of this series apply in the coronal limit, although the formalism will go to equilibrium in high densities. Figure 10, 11, and 12 in Ferland et al. (2017) display the coronal limit for collisionally ionized and photoionized cases. For iron ($Z=26$), the coronal limit applies for electron densities smaller than 10^{16} cm^{-3} .

The organization of this Chapter is as follows. Section 4.2 discusses the theoretical framework of Case A, B, C, and D. Section 4.3 lists the simulation parameters used for our calculations. Section 4.4 describes the results. Section 4.5 discusses the total emitted spectrum within the energy range 0.1 - 10 keV. Section 4.6 describes the effects of background continuum opacities like electron scattering opacity. Section 4.7 discusses our results. We refer to the transitions going from $n = 2, 3, 4$ to $n = 1$ in H-like iron as $Ly\alpha$, $Ly\beta$, and $Ly\gamma$ and in He-like iron as $K\alpha$, $K\beta$, and $K\gamma$. Transitions going from $n = 3$ to $n = 2$ are called $H\alpha$ in H-like iron and $L\alpha$ in He-like iron. This nomenclature is inspired by Siegbahn notation (Siegbahn, 1916) as implemented in, for instance, Gabriel (1972), Fukumura and Tsuruta (2004), and Koyama et al. (2007).

4.2 Theoretical Framework

Lines are formed under Case A, Case B, Case C, or Case D conditions. Case A and Case B occur in collisionally ionized clouds. Case A, Case B, Case C, and Case D occur in photoionized clouds. Figure 4.1 shows the four cases for the two ionizing conditions. Line formation processes in collisionally ionized clouds have been discussed in the first two papers of this series. This paper solely focuses on photoionized clouds.

A schematic representation of all four cases is shown in Figure 4.2 for a simplified three-level system. Small-column-density (optically thin) regions can be described by Case A or Case C depending on the ionizing radiation. In both cases, line photons escape the cloud without any scattering. Case A occurs when the continuum radiation hitting the cloud has strong absorption features in the Lyman lines. There is no continuum pumping in the Lyman lines emitted by the cloud. Lines in the Case A limit are solely formed by radiative recombination and cascades from higher

Figure 4.1: A flow-chart showing the line formation conditions occurring in photoionized/collisionally ionized clouds. Case A, Case B, Case C, and Case D occur in photoionized clouds. Case A and Case B also occur in collisionally ionized clouds.

levels¹. Case C occurs if the continuum source striking the optically thin cloud does not contain Lyman absorption lines, and the emitted Lyman lines are enhanced by continuum pumping. As a result, Case C spectrum is always brighter than Case A.

The ratio of the Case C to Case A line intensities can be calculated from the ratio of continuum pumping rate to the rate of recombination (r). In equilibrium, r is equal to the rate of photoionization (Γ_n):

$$\Gamma_n = \int_{\nu_o}^{\infty} \frac{4\pi J_\nu}{h\nu} \alpha_\nu d\nu \quad [\text{s}^{-1}] \quad (4.1)$$

where J_ν [$\text{erg cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{sr}^{-1} \text{Hz}^{-1}$] is the mean intensity per unit frequency, per unit solid angle of the incident radiation, α_ν is the photoionization cross-section [cm^2] for the atom/ion by photons of energy $h\nu$.

The rate of continuum pumping of a line from level l to level u is given by:

$$\Gamma_l = B_{lu} J_l = f_{lu} \frac{\pi e^2}{mc} \left(\frac{4\pi J_l}{h\nu} \right) \quad [\text{s}^{-1}] \quad (4.2)$$

where B_{lu} is the Einstein coefficient, f_{lu} is the oscillator strength, and the other symbols have their usual meanings.

For a power-law ($f_\nu \propto \nu^{-1}$) model in H-like iron for Lyman- α transition in a simple two-level system:

$$\frac{\Gamma_l}{r} \sim 16 \quad (4.3)$$

¹As described in Chakraborty et al. (2020c), in a collisionally ionized cloud in the absence of photoionizing radiation line formation in optically thin limit is also described by Case A.

Figure 4.2: A simplified three-level representation of Case A, Case B, Case C, and Case D shown for a H-like system. The same atomic processes occur in He-like systems too. The top-left panel shows Case A, where the lines are formed by radiative recombination and cascades from higher levels. There is no continuum pumping. The cloud is optically thin, and all Lyman photons escape the cloud without scattering/absorption. The top-right panel shows Case B, where the cloud is optically thick, and continuum pumping photons are blocked. Higher n -Lyman photons (Ly β in the diagram) scatter multiple times to generate Balmer (here H α) and Ly α photons. The bottom-left panel shows Case C, where in addition to radiative recombination and downward cascade, Lyman lines are also enhanced by continuum pumping. The enhanced Lyman lines escape the optically thin cloud. The bottom-right panel shows Case D, where multiple scatterings and continuum pumping in Lyman lines occur together in an optically thick cloud. Two-photon-continuum is not shown because it does not make emission lines.

Figure 4.3: Ionization in iron versus log of ionization parameter (U). Top and bottom panels show the iron ionization in linear and log scales. Red, blue, green, and magenta lines show the fraction of no-electron, H-like, He-like, and Li-like iron. A vertical black line is drawn at $\log U = 2$ in the linear plot, the ionization parameter chosen for our calculations. The x-axes on the top in both figures show $\log \xi$.

This implies that, $\text{Ly}\alpha$ line intensities are ~ 16 times enhanced in Case C compared to Case A. The calculated ratio is approximate, as the real calculation will have many pumping lines and many different branching ratios. This ratio is approximately in agreement with the line intensities listed in Table 4.1 obtained from our CLOUDY simulations, which shows that the Case C $\text{Ly}\alpha$ in H-like iron is ~ 10 times enhanced than Case A.

In contrast, Case B occurs in the high-column-density limit ($N_{\text{H}} \geq 10^{21.5} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). In this limit, Lyman line optical depths are large enough for photons to undergo multiple scatterings and so are converted into $\text{H}\alpha$ (or $\text{L}\alpha$) and $\text{Ly}\alpha$ (or $\text{K}\alpha$) photons or two-photon-continuum. The cloud becomes self-shielding, stopping the continuum pumping despite the presence of a continuum radiation source in the cloud. Typically, Case B describes the line formation in most observed optically thick nebulae (Osterbrock and Ferland, 2006).

Case D occurs if Lyman line optical depths are large, but the cloud does not entirely become self-shielding to the external radiation. Luridiana et al. (2009) argued that a real nebula in the optically thick limit would be better represented by Case D than Case B. Their study reported a significant contribution of continuum pumping on Balmer emissivity in the HII region. As far as we know, Case D had not been studied in the X-ray to date. Our calculations for the X-ray regime in the optically thick limit show substantial enhancement in the Lyman and Balmer line intensities in H- and He-like iron. This will be further elaborated in Section 4.4.4.

Figure 4.4: Temperature of the photoionized cloud versus log of ionization parameter ($\log U$) for a 1 cm^3 plasma. The black dashed lines show the temperature at our choice of ionization parameter, $\log U = 2$. The x-axis on the top shows $\log \xi$.

4.3 Simulation Parameters

This section discusses the simulation parameters used in CLOUDY. We aim to establish a standard mathematical framework of line formation through Case A, Case B, Case C, and Case D. The simulation parameters have been chosen accordingly. All the simulations are done using the development version of CLOUDY with a hydrogen density of 1 cm^{-3} . To make the simplest case, the shape of the incident radiation field is assumed to be a power-law spectral energy distribution (SED):

$$f_\nu \propto \nu^{-\alpha} \quad (4.4)$$

with $\alpha = 1$.

The intensity of the radiation field is characterized by ionization parameter (U), defined with the following ratio:

$$U = \frac{\Phi_H}{n_H c} \quad (4.5)$$

where Φ_H is flux of hydrogen-ionizing photons, n_H is the hydrogen-density, and c is the speed of light.

Much of the X-ray literature uses the ξ ionization parameter defined by Kallman and Bautista (2001). For our $\alpha = 1$ SED, $\xi = 1$ corresponds to an U of 0.01767.

Figure 4.3 shows the variation of different ionization stages in iron with the log of U . The top x-axis shows the log of ξ . The top panel of the figure shows a linear plot, and the bottom panel shows a log plot. We choose $\log U = 2$ ($\log \xi = 3.75$) to maximize the quantity of H- and He-like iron in the cloud. This also minimizes

the overlap between He- and Li-like iron ions, as Li-like iron selectively changes the He-like spectra by line interlocking (Chakraborty et al., 2020b). The linear figure also shows our choice of ionization parameter with a black vertical line. Note that, our choice of ionization parameter is in agreement with the range of ξ mentioned in Kallman et al. (2004) ($\log \xi \geq 2$) for highly charged iron, who also discussed K lines in iron in a photoionized cloud for a power-law SED.

The cloud temperature (T) is obtained from the energy equilibrium equation from a heating cooling balance to replicate the actual physical temperature of a photoionized cloud. The computed temperature is - $T \sim 6 \times 10^6$ K at $\log U = 2$. The variation of T with $\log U$ is shown in Figure 4.4. Note that, photoionized clouds are a lot cooler than collisionally ionized clouds. In fact, this equilibrium temperature is ~ 8 times smaller than that of the collisionally ionized plasma considered in Chapters 2 and 3.

Table 4.1: Line intensities per unit thickness (I/d) for Case A, B, C, and D conditions for certain Lyman and Balmer transitions in H- and He-like ions in a photoionized cloud. I/d's for Case A and C are listed for $N_H=10^{19}$ cm^{-2} and for Case B and D are listed for $N_H = 10^{24}$ cm^{-2} . The I/d's listed under Case A, Case B, Case C, and Case D are what will be observed in nature. The Case B_{classic}, the classic Menzel-Baker Case B, has also been included in the table for educational purposes.

Transitions	Wavelength	I/d [$\text{erg cm}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$]				
		Case A	Case B _{classic}	Case B	Case C	Case D
H-like						
$2^2P \rightarrow 1^2S$	1.77982 Å	6.22e-25	8.24e-25	3.05e-25	6.05e-24	4.15e-25
$3^2P \rightarrow 1^2S$	1.50273 Å	1.43e-25	2.84e-26	1.57e-26	9.06e-25	2.69e-26
$3^2P \rightarrow 2^2S$	9.65247 Å	4.99e-26	8.94e-26	4.89e-26	7.17e-26	6.68e-26
$4^2P \rightarrow 1^2S$	1.42505 Å	5.55e-26	1.05e-26	9.67e-27	3.07e-25	1.89e-26
$4^2P \rightarrow 2^2S$	7.14920 Å	1.86e-26	3.09e-26	1.69e-26	2.71e-26	2.05e-26
He-like						
$2^1P \rightarrow 1^1S(w)$	1.85040 Å	1.69e-25	1.74e-25	1.29e-25	4.35e-24	2.69e-25
$2^3P_2 \rightarrow 1^1S(x)$	1.85541 Å	2.41e-25	2.46e-25	1.85e-25	2.59e-25	2.02e-25
$2^3P_1 \rightarrow 1^1S(y)$	1.85951 Å	1.82e-25	1.89e-25	1.59e-25	5.77e-25	1.97e-25
$2^3S \rightarrow 1^1S(z)$	1.86819 Å	2.68e-25	3.72e-25	4.23e-25	4.12e-25	4.83e-25
$3^1P \rightarrow 1^1S$	1.57317 Å	4.53e-26	1.36e-26	8.89e-27	7.32e-25	2.74e-26
$3^3P \rightarrow 1^1S$	1.57456 Å	9.81e-26	1.45e-26	1.23e-26	3.09e-25	1.68e-26
$3^1P \rightarrow 2^1S$	10.2202 Å	4.41e-28	5.53e-27	5.41e-27	7.14e-27	9.72e-27
$3^3P \rightarrow 2^3S$	10.0178 Å	6.96e-27	1.91e-26	1.87e-26	2.19e-26	2.82e-26
$4^1P \rightarrow 1^1S$	1.49460 Å	1.82e-26	8.28e-27	5.37e-27	2.51e-25	1.92e-26
$4^3P \rightarrow 1^1S$	1.49513 Å	3.61e-26	9.36e-27	7.77e-27	1.06e-25	1.19e-26
$4^1P \rightarrow 2^1S$	7.61825 Å	2.40e-28	1.73e-27	1.68e-27	3.32e-27	3.77e-27
$4^3P \rightarrow 2^3S$	7.48713 Å	3.24e-27	6.91e-27	6.78e-27	9.54e-27	1.11e-26

Figure 4.5: Line intensity per unit thickness of the cloud versus the log of hydrogen column density. Figures in the top panel show Case A to Case B transition in H- and He-like iron. Dashed lines represent the classic Menzel-Baker Case A to Case B limit, solid lines represent the observed Case A to Case B limit. Figures in the bottom panel show the observed Case C to Case D transition in H- and He-like iron.

4.4 Results

This section explores different conditions for the lines to form in the presence of a photoionizing source emitting in X-rays. Table 4.1 shows a comparison between selective line intensities (including the $K\alpha$ complex) for Case A, Case B, Case C, and Case D conditions for H- and He-like iron. The quantity listed in the table is the line intensity (I) per unit thickness (d), I/d. As the line intensities increase as the cloud’s size/thickness increases, I/d tracks the scaled change in the line intensities for all four cases or the transition between them. Although I/d has the same units as the emissivity of a line, $4\pi j$, it does not have the same physical interpretation. All the I/d’s listed in Table 4.1 are observed in nature except for the Case B_{classic}, which will be further discussed in section 4.4.2. Line wavelengths listed in the table are taken from NIST² (version 5.8: Kramida et al., 2018).

The low-column-density (optically thin) limit represents Case A and C, and the high-column-density (optically thick) limit represents Case B and D. Therefore, I/d’s listed in the table for Case A and C are computed at $N_H=10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and for Case B and D at $N_H=10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The continuous variation of I/d with hydrogen column density and the transition from Case A to B and Case C to D are shown in Figure 4.5.

4.4.1 Case A

The schematic representation of Case A is shown in the upper-left panel of Figure 4.2. Case A is the simplest of all four cases occurring in optically thin systems. As mentioned in the introduction, Case A was developed for SEDs with strong Lyman absorption features, for example, stellar SEDs. The strong Lyman absorption lines in the SED prevent the continuum pumping. The continuum pumping in our simulated cloud is stopped using the CLOUDY command:

```
no induced processes
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The top panel of Figure 4.5 shows that I/d in H- and He-like iron remains constant up to $\sim N_H=10^{21.5} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. This is because up to this column density, Lyman lines escape without any scattering/absorption, and any column density smaller than $N_H=10^{21.5} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ will generate a pure Case A spectrum. Table 4.1 shows I/d for Case A at $N_H=10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

4.4.2 Case B

The top-right panel of Figure 4.2 shows the Case B condition in a cloud. The continuum pumping is disabled as in 4.4.1. As shown in Figure 4.5, the column densities bigger than $N_H \sim 10^{21.5} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ begin to make a transition to the Case B limit. Two types of Case B have been shown - Case B_{classic} and Case B. The dashed and solid lines in the top panel of Figure 4.5 represent Case B_{classic} and Case B, respectively. What we refer to as Case B throughout the text considers all the physical processes

²<https://physics.nist.gov/asd>

Figure 4.6: Optical depth versus log of hydrogen column density for important $\text{Ly}\alpha$, $\text{Ly}\beta$, and $\text{Ly}\gamma$ transitions in H- iron, and $\text{K}\alpha$, $\text{K}\beta$, and $\text{K}\gamma$ transitions in He-like iron. Low-column-density limit represents Case A or Case C. High-column-density limit represents Case B or Case D.

observed in nature in the X-ray limit, including electron scattering and line overlap. The concept of electron scattering is described later in this section and in section 4.6. Case $\text{B}_{\text{classic}}$ is the Menzel-Baker Case B values studied in the 1930's that does not include electron scattering and line overlap. In CLOUDY, electron scattering can be disabled with the following command:

```
no electron scattering
```

We find that, for X-ray emission from H- and He-like iron, Case $\text{B}_{\text{classic}}$ remains a pedagogical scenario.

Table 4.1 shows the I/d values for Case $\text{B}_{\text{classic}}$ and Case B (observed in nature) at $N_H=10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. In the typical Menzel-Baker Case $\text{B}_{\text{classic}}$, as a consequence of conversion of higher-n Lyman lines into $\text{Ly}\alpha$ (or $\text{K}\alpha$) and Balmer lines, $\text{Ly}\alpha$ (or $\text{K}\alpha$) intensity increases, $\text{Ly}\beta$ (or $\text{K}\beta$) and higher-n Lyman line intensities decrease, and $\text{H}\alpha$ (or $\text{L}\alpha$) and higher-order Balmer line intensities increase compared to the Case A limit. Case $\text{B}_{\text{classic}}$ column in the table exactly reflects this behaviour both for H- and He-like iron. For instance in H-like iron, I/d in $\text{Ly}\alpha$ increases by $\sim 32\%$, $\text{Ly}\beta$ decreases by $\sim 80\%$, and $\text{H}\alpha$ increases by $\sim 80\%$ at $N_H=10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. In He-like iron, I/d in z increases by $\sim 40\%$, x, y, and w increase very slightly ($\leq 4\%$), $\text{K}\beta$ decreases by $\sim 3 - 7$ times, and $\text{L}\alpha$ increases by $\sim 3 - 13$ times compared to Case A.

However, the observed Case B values are quite different from the Case $\text{B}_{\text{classic}}$ values. In fact, in H-like iron, all Lyman I/d values decrease compared to the Case A limit, including $\text{Ly}\alpha$. H-like $\text{Ly}\alpha$ decreases by $\sim 50\%$. In He-like iron, selected $\text{K}\alpha$ lines (x, y, and w) show a decrease up to $\sim 24\%$.

Such decrease in the line intensities in the observed Case B mainly occurs due to electron scattering, as described in section 4.6. When line photons scatter off

high-speed electrons, they are largely Doppler-shifted from their line-center. Lines with the largest optical depths are more likely to exhibit a reduction in their line intensities as they are more likely to scatter. Figure 4.6 shows the optical depth of certain Lyman and Balmer lines in H- and He-like iron. In H-like iron, Ly α , Ly β , and Ly γ intensities are reduced due to electron scattering because of their large optical depths. In He-like iron, w, y, K β , and K γ intensities are reduced. The optical depth in z is negligible at $N_H=10^{24}$ cm $^{-2}$, and thus I/d for z is not affected by electron scattering. The reduction in I/d for x is not due to electron scattering but a series of processes described in the appendix of Chakraborty et al. (2020b). This explains the observed Case B behavior both in Table 4.1 and Figure 4.5.

4.4.3 Case C

The bottom-left panel of Figure 4.2 represents the Case C condition in a photoionized cloud. Case C occurs in optically thin clouds, like Case A. However, the Case C spectrum is enhanced by the continuum pumping/fluorescence and makes the brightest spectrum of all four cases. This can be seen in Table 4.1 and the bottom panel of Figure 4.5. The degree of enhancement depends on the shape of the incident radiation field (Ferland, 1999). In our case, a power-law SED fluoresces the cloud (refer to section 4.3 for details).

The enhancement in the I/d values in Case C is measured with respect to the Case A spectrum. From the CLOUDY simulation listed in Table 4.1, we find that the I/d for Case C for the Ly α transition for H-like iron gets ~ 10 times amplified compared to that of Case A. This approximately agrees with the theoretical value of amplification shown in section 4.2. Both Ly β and Ly γ lines get amplified by ~ 6 times. Further, our calculation for He-like iron shows that w is enhanced ~ 27 times, x, y, and z are enhanced ~ 1.1 , 3.2, and 1.5 times, respectively. The K β and K γ transitions are enhanced by $\sim 3 - 16$ times and $\sim 3 - 14$ times, respectively. The Balmer lines are enhanced up to ~ 16 times.

4.4.4 Case D

The Case D condition in the cloud is shown in the bottom-right panel of Figure 4.3, where continuum pumping and multiple scatterings happen together. The cloud is partially self-shielded, and lines are partially enhanced by incident radiation. Case D has been hardly discussed in the literature, as at the very high column densities, a cloud can become entirely self-shielded, and there is essentially no Case D. The spectral behavior is described by Case B in such cases.

Case D becomes useful when the cloud's column density is high enough to allow multiple scatterings but can not entirely stop the continuum radiation from penetrating the cloud. In fact we find that, for X-ray emission from H- and He-like plasma, Case D deviates considerably from Case B even at a column density as high as $N_H=10^{24}$ cm $^{-2}$. As shown in Table 4.1 at $N_H=10^{24}$ cm $^{-2}$, the observed Case D value of I/d for H-like iron is $\sim 36\%$ enhanced in Ly α , $\sim 71\%$ enhanced in Ly β , and $\sim 37\%$ enhanced in H α compared to the observed Case B value. In He-like iron, w,

x, y, and z are enhanced $\sim 109\%$, $\sim 9\%$, $\sim 24\%$, and $\sim 14\%$, respectively. $K\beta$ is enhanced by $\sim 208\%$ (for $3^1P \rightarrow 1^1S$), and $\sim 37\%$ (for $3^3P \rightarrow 1^1S$), respectively. $L\alpha$ is enhanced $\sim 80\%$ (for $3^1P \rightarrow 2^1S$), and $\sim 51\%$ (for $3^3P \rightarrow 2^3S$), respectively.

The future microcalorimeters will detect ever-so-slight changes in the spectra, thanks to their unmatched spectral resolution. Thus it becomes crucial to understand the Case D behavior in optically thick irradiated clouds and its deviation from Case B, especially for column densities $N_H \leq 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Needless to say, at even bigger column densities when the optical depth becomes very large the external radiation will be completely absorbed in the gas. Case D values will eventually approach the Case B values. But until the cloud is thick enough to stop continuum pumping entirely, Case D will be the best description of the emission spectra in irradiated clouds.

4.4.5 Case A/Case C to Case B/Case D transition

What drives the Case A to Case B or Case C to Case D transition in a real astronomical scenario is the variation in column density from low-column-density (optically thin) to high-column-density (optically thick) limit. Figure 4.5 shows these transitions for H-like and He-like iron in a photoionized cloud.

When Case A and B were first discussed in the 1930s, the source of the radiation was assumed to be stellar with strong Lyman absorption lines and no continuum pumping. Thus, galactic nebulae with strong absorption features show Case A to Case B transition under the variation in column density. Case A to Case B transition also occurs in any collisionally ionized cloud, as discussed in Chapters 2 and 3, and also in Chakraborty et al. (2020b,c). Chakraborty et al. (2020c) showed that the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ line ratios calculated with CLOUDY are in excellent agreement with the line ratios observed by *Hitomi* for the outer region of Perseus core (see figure 14 in their paper). At the best-fit hydrogen column density of the hot gas at Perseus core ($N_{H,\text{hot}} = 1.88 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) reported by Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018a), line formation processes can be best described by Case A.

In extragalactic environments, such as a cloud photoionized by an Active galactic nucleus (AGN) SED with no Lyman absorption lines, the line formation in the low-column-density limit will be described by Case C in the optically thin limit and Case D in the optically thick limit until the cloud becomes very optically thick to stop continuum pumping.

Figure 4.7 shows the variation of I/d in H-like iron with hydrogen column density for the most complex system observed in nature (Case C to D transition) to the simplest possible system (Case A to B_{classic} transition). Case C to B transition shows the observed I/d values in an irradiated cloud, which includes continuum pumping and electron scattering. Case A to B transition shows the observed I/d with no continuum pumping. Case A to B_{classic} shows the classical Menzel-Baker transition with no continuum pumping and no electron scattering.

Figure 4.7: Case C to D, Case A to B, and Case A to B_{classic} transitions shown in the same figure for an irradiated cloud in $\text{Ly}\alpha$ for H-like iron. The three curves shown in this figure were plotted separately in the left panel of Figure 4.5 along with other lines. Case C to D transition curve includes continuum pumping and electron scattering. Case A to B transition curve includes electron scattering but no continuum pumping. Case A to B_{classic} transition curve does not include continuum pumping or electron scattering, and is the simplest of all three cases.

4.5 Description of spectral features

Figure 4.8 shows the total observed X-ray spectrum coming from a photoionized cloud for Case A, B, C, and D within the energy range 0.1-10 keV. The spectrum is generated at the resolving power of XRISM ($R \sim 1200$) at 6 keV set to CLOUDY. Similar to section 4.4, the y axis of the figure has been scaled to show the total emission (νF_ν) per unit thickness (d) of the cloud, $\nu F_\nu/d$. νF_ν is a sum of the total continuum emission and discrete line intensity (I) multiplied by R :

$$\nu F_\nu = \nu F_\nu^{\text{continuum}} + RI \quad (4.6)$$

In CLOUDY, νF_ν can be stored with the following command:

```
save emitted continuum
```

added to the input script.

The top and bottom rows in Figure 4.8 overplots the total emission spectrum for Case A with Case C, and Case B with Case D. The column densities set to the cloud for calculating the spectra are the same as section 4.4. Left and right panels show the same plots linear and log scale, respectively. Clearly, Case C is enhanced compared to the Case A spectrum due to continuum pumping. Case D is also brighter than Case B due to partial continuum pumping.

Figure 4.8: The total scaled emission spectrum for Case A, B, C, and D conditions within the energy range 0.1-10 keV at the resolving power of *XRISM* ($R \sim 1200$) around 6 keV. Top-left and top-right panels show Case A (green) and Case C (red) spectrum in linear and log scale. Bottom-left and bottom-right panels show Case B (blue) and Case D (magenta) spectrum in linear and log scale. Case C is brighter than Case A due to continuum pumping, and Case D is brighter than Case B due to partial continuum pumping.

Figure 4.9: A pedagogical simplified Case D spectrum for a hydrogen and iron only model. Lyman and Balmer lines in H- and He- like iron are marked with black dashed lines. Ionization edges (I.E.) for H-and He-like iron are shown with blue dashed lines.

Figure 4.9 shows a simplified plot for a hydrogen and iron only model under Case D condition. This is not what is observed in nature. The purpose of this figure is to look at the components of the spectra coming from H- and He-like iron in a less complicated form. The Lyman and Balmer lines are marked with black, and the ionization edges (I.E.) of H-like and He-like iron at ~ 9.3 keV and ~ 8.8 keV are marked with blue.

4.6 Additional factors changing the line intensities

The background continuum opacity of the photoionized cloud consists of two types of opacities - absorption opacity and scattering opacity. Figure 4.10 shows these two types of opacities. Absorption opacity mostly comes from the photoelectric absorption/photoionization opacity.³ Near the K α complex, absorption opacity is many orders of magnitude smaller than the scattering opacity, making it unimportant without affecting the line spectrum. Thus we only discuss the effects of scattering opacity.

Scattering opacity mostly comes from the scattering of line photons by high-speed thermal electrons that lead to a process called electron scattering escape (ESE). The concept of ESE has been elaborated in Section 2.7, and also in Chakraborty et al. (2020b).

³Other absorption opacities like bremsstrahlung opacity and dust opacity are negligible as bremsstrahlung opacity depends on the density square, which is very small (1 cm^{-3}), and we assume no dust is present in our model.

Figure 4.10: Continuum background opacities in a photoionized iron and hydrogen only model. Red solid line shows the total scattering opacity. Blue line shows the total absorption opacity.

As a result of scattering off high-speed electrons, a fraction of the line photons is largely Doppler-shifted from their line-center. These Doppler-shifted photons create super-broad Gaussian profiles. The observed spectrum will include these broad Gaussian profiles as well as the actual sharp line profiles for the fraction of photons that were not scattered (Miller et al., 2002; Hanke et al., 2009).

In CLOUDY, these broad Gaussian profiles can be excluded with the following CLOUDY command⁴:

```
no scattering intensity
```

reporting only the intensities of the sharp line profiles.

Figure 4.11 shows the total scaled emission near the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. For simplicity, widths of the sharp line profiles are assumed to be coming from the thermal velocity of the iron ions only. The presence of turbulence will change the widths of the sharp components, but the physics of electron scattering will be the same. At $T = 6 \times 10^6$ K, the temperature of our simulated cloud, the FWHM of these sharp line profiles at $E \sim 6.7$ keV are: $\Delta E_{\text{FWHM}}^{\text{sharp}} = 2 \sqrt{\ln 2} \frac{u_{\text{Dop}}}{c} E \sim 1.6$ eV, where $u_{\text{Dop}} = \sqrt{\frac{2kT}{m_{\text{Fe}}}} \sim 43$ km/s. At the same temperature, FWHM of the broad line profiles are $\Delta E_{\text{FWHM}}^{\text{broad}} \sim 0.5$ keV, where $u_{\text{Dop}} = \sqrt{\frac{2kT}{m_e}} \sim 13500$ km/s. This implies that, the height of broad Gaussians will be orders of magnitude smaller than the sharp components, and are difficult to detect by telescopes (Torrejón et al., 2010).

⁴This is a new CLOUDY command that counts the intensity of the remaining line photons that didn't suffer electron scattering. The next update to the release version of CLOUDY, C17.03, will include this command.

The left panel in Figure 4.11 shows the changes in the total scaled emission in a log scale for the hydrogen column densities $N_H = 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, 10^{22} cm^{-2} , and 10^{24} cm^{-2} in the presence of continuum pumping. The broad Gaussians shown in the figure are solely from the electron scattering of the photons in Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. We do not show the broad Gaussians from the other lines to keep the figure simple.

The right panel shows a zoomed-in version of the sharp line profiles for all three column densities on a linear scale. As the continuum pumping is present, $\nu F_\nu/d$ at $N_H = 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ represents the Case C limit, and $N_H = 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ represents the Case D limit.

It can be seen from the figure that w line intensity reduces significantly with the increase in optical depth/column density. There are two factors responsible for this reduction. First, the continuum pumping begins to become partially blocked with the increase in optical depth. Second, w has the largest line-optical depth among all He-like transitions and is more likely to suffer electron scattering. Of course, when observed by future high-resolution telescopes like *XRISM* and *Athena*, the electron scattered broad Gaussian component of w will be much fainter than the sharp component. But the reduction in the sharp w line intensity (or line intensity of any resonance line) with increasing optical depth can serve as a powerful optical depth/column density diagnostic.

Note that, Gilfanov et al. (1987) discussed the effects of resonance scattering and showed the distortion in radial surface brightness profile due to migration of resonance X-ray line photons from the cluster center to the outer region. This will lead to a suppression in line fluxes in the central region of a cluster. For example, in Perseus, this factor was reported to be ~ 1.3 for w ($\tau \sim 1$) near the cluster center by Hitomi Collaboration et al. (2018b). Of course, the suppression factor will be different in other systems depending on the geometry and optical depth.

Our calculations presented in this Chapter represent a general study for a photoionized system irradiated with a power-law SED. From our CLOUDY calculations, the suppression in w line intensity at $\tau = 1$ is ~ 1.43 due to the joint contribution of partial continuum pumping and electron scattering. Therefore it is safe to say that, the change in the resonance line intensities due to these two factors can be as important as the resonance scattering effects. Our current model predicts the total emission from a symmetric geometry, so scattering has no effect on the emergent intensity. In addition to what we report in this paper, the Gilfanov et al. (1987) resonance scattering geometric correction has to be applied to match with the observed spectra.

4.7 Discussion and Conclusion

- Line formation processes were broadly categorized into two cases in the 1930s - Case A and Case B (Menzel, 1937; Menzel and Baker, 1937; Baker and Menzel, 1938; Baker et al., 1938). At that time, the SED ionizing the cloud was assumed to have strong Lyman absorption lines. There was no continuum pumping/fluorescence to enhance the spectra. Some examples are O-stars in starburst galaxies, planetary nebulae etc. (Osterbrock and Ferland, 2006).

Figure 4.11: The left panel shows the total scaled emission (sharp line profiles + continuum including the broad line profiles) in a log scale at $N_{\text{H}} = 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, 10^{22} cm^{-2} , and 10^{24} cm^{-2} in presence of continuum pumping. The broad Gaussians shown in the figure come from the photons in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex scattered off high-speed electrons and Doppler-shifted from their line-centers. The sharp line profiles come from the originally emitted line photons in the photoionized cloud that are not affected by electron scattering. The $N_{\text{H}} = 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ case has significant optical depth for electron scattering which depresses the continuum. The right panel is a zoomed-in version of the left panel around the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex. The emission in w significantly reduces with increase in column density. The emission in y reduces slightly.

But in extragalactic environments such as a cloud photoionized by an AGN SED, or galaxies with quasars with no Lyman absorption lines, continuum pumping will significantly enhance the spectra. This led to the discovery of a third case in the late 1930 s - Case C (Baker et al., 1938), which describes optically thin clouds in the presence of continuum pumping. A fourth case - Case D was discovered recently (Luridiana et al., 2009), which describes spectra from an optically thick cloud in the presence of continuum pumping.

- Figure 4.3 shows the schematic representation of all four cases.
 - Under Case A condition, lines are formed by radiative recombination and cascades from higher levels. Lyman lines escape the optically thin cloud without scattering/absorption.
 - Case B occurs when higher-n Lyman lines are converted to Balmer lines and $\text{Ly}\alpha$ (or $\text{K}\alpha$) or two-photon-continuum due to multiple scatterings in an optically thick cloud.
 - Lines are formed under Case C when Lyman lines are enhanced by continuum pumping and freely escape the optically thin cloud.

- Case D occurs when multiple scattering and continuum pumping in Lyman lines occur together in an optically thick cloud so that the lines are partially enhanced.
- This Chapter is dedicated to understanding line formation processes through Case A, Case B, Case C, and Case D in the X-ray emitting photoionized plasma with CLOUDY. We study H- and He-like iron emitting in the X-ray with improved CLOUDY energies in excellent agreement with the future microcalorimeter observations (Chakraborty et al., 2020a). In our simulations, we use a power-law SED to illuminate the cloud, and an equilibrium temperature of 6×10^6 K computed from the heating-cooling balance. Refer to section 4.3 for details on simulation parameters. As the absolute line intensities (I) increase with cloud thickness (d), we compare line intensity per unit thickness of the cloud (I/d) for estimating the scaled difference between all four cases.
- Table 4.1 lists the line intensity (I) per unit thickness (d) of the cloud, I/d, for the Case A, Case B, Case C, and Case D conditions observed in nature. To generate the optically thin and optically thick conditions in the cloud, I/d's for Case A and C are computed at $N_H=10^{19}$ cm⁻², and for Case B and D are computed at $N_H=10^{24}$ cm⁻², respectively. The Menzel-Baker Case B values are listed under the Case B_{classic} column in the table. Ly α in H-like iron and K α in He-like iron in Case B_{classic} are enhanced compared to their corresponding Case A values due to the conversion of higher n-Lyman lines into Ly α (or K α) plus Balmer lines. But in real astronomical sources, the presence of electron scattering reduces the observed Case B values. In H-like iron, I/d for Ly α decreases by $\sim 50\%$. In He-like iron, x, y, and w exhibit a decrease up to $\sim 24\%$. Case C values are the brightest of all four cases due to the free escape of Lyman photons following continuum pumping. The Ly α and K α transitions in H- and He-like iron are up to ~ 10 and ~ 27 times enhanced compared to the corresponding Case A values. Case D values are smaller than Case C values but bigger than the Case B values, as they are partially enhanced by continuum pumping. For H like iron, Case D I/d for Ly α is $\sim 36\%$ enhanced compared to the corresponding Case B value. Ly β is $\sim 71\%$ enhanced, H α is $\sim 36\%$ enhanced. In He-like iron, K α is enhanced up to $\sim 109\%$, K β is enhanced up to $\sim 208\%$, L α is enhanced up to $\sim 80\%$.
- The total emission spectrum for Case A, B, C, and D conditions within the energy range 0.1-10 keV have been shown in Figure 4.8. They include the continuum emission as well as the line emission described in the previous paragraphs. The resolving power (R) for our CLOUDY simulations is set at $R \sim 1200$, which is the resolving power of X $RISM$ at ~ 6 keV. The figure shows Case A overplotted with Case C and Case B overplotted with Case D in linear and log scale. Clearly, the line emissions in the Case C spectrum are brighter than Case A, and line emissions in the Case D spectrum are brighter than Case B due to continuum pumping and partial continuum pumping, respectively.

- Electron scattering opacity can play an important role in deciding the line intensities in optically thick clouds. Line intensities for Case B and Case D can be reduced because of this. The top panel of Figure 4.5 and Table 4.1 showed the deviation of the observed Case B values, which includes the effect of electron scattering, from Case B_{classic}, which does not include electron scattering. I/d values shown in Table 4.1 and the bottom panel of Figure 4.5 for Case D also include electron scattering.
- Due to the electron scattering opacity, the line photons are scattered off high-speed electrons and are Doppler shifted from their line-center. These scattered photons form Gaussians with super-broad-bases. The line photons that are not scattered have a sharp base equivalent to their thermal width (and turbulent width if turbulence is present). Figure 4.11 shows these sharp and broad components coming from Fe XXV K α complex in the presence of continuum pumping for the hydrogen column densities $N_H = 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, 10^{22} cm^{-2} , and 10^{24} cm^{-2} . $N_H = 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ is the Case C limit, and $N_H = 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ is the Case D limit. The broad components will be much fainter than the sharp components when detected by high-resolution telescopes. The observed sharp components for the resonance lines will exhibit significant changes in their line-fluxes with variation in column density (and optical depth). It can be seen in Figure 4.11 that, the w line-intensity decreases significantly with an increase in column density. Such reduction in w is due to the two following factors - a) Continuum pumping becomes partially blocked with the increase in optical depth. b) The large optical depth of w makes it more likely to be scattered by electrons. A combination of a) & b) will reduce the line intensity of w or any resonance line significantly with the increase in column density, which can serve as a powerful diagnostic in measuring the column density/optical depth of the cloud.

From our CLOUDY simulation, we get the suppression in w line intensity due to the two above factors at $\tau = 1$ to be ~ 1.43 , which is as important as the resonance scattering effects described by Gilfanov et al. (1987). As our current CLOUDY model assumes a symmetric geometry, the effects of resonance scattering are not included in our calculation. A real observed spectrum will correspond to a resonance-scattering corrected CLOUDY-generated spectrum shown in this paper.

- After the discovery of Case A and B, these two cases have been widely discussed in the literature for the optical, UV, and infrared regimes, with limited studies on X-rays. As far as we know, there has been no discussion on X-ray spectra under Case C and Case D condition. Case D is the least discussed of all four cases, as ideally, at very high column densities, Case D should be no different than Case B values, as mentioned in section 4.4.4. But Table 4.1 and bottom panel of Figure 4.8 shows that, even at a column density as high as $N_H = 10^{24} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ in a cloud illuminated with a power-law SED, Case D deviates considerably from Case B for X-ray emission from H- and He-like iron. This deviation will certainly be detected by the future high-resolution telescopes with

microcalorimeter technology.

We emphasize the fact that Case C and Case D deserve far more attention than they have been given to date, especially because they could be the best representation of the emission spectra from irradiated extragalactic sources with a broad range of column densities.

Chapter 5 Optical depth effects on the soft X-rays studied with Cloudy in collisionally ionized and photoionized plasma

5.1 Introduction

The strongest emission lines observed in the soft X-ray spectra are H-like and He-like lines from elements between carbon and sulfur, and Fe L-shell lines. X-ray emitting plasmas can be collisionally-ionized or photoionized. In collisionally-ionized plasma, ionization or excitation events mainly occur due to electron-ion collisions. In photoionized plasma, ionization is dominated by the interaction between photons and ions/atoms. A hybrid of the two types of plasma is also possible, where the cloud is partly collisionally-ionized and partly photoionized.

Line intensity in observed X-ray spectra can be enhanced or suppressed depending on the following factors. If photoionized, lines will be a) enhanced by continuum pumping unless there are Lyman absorption lines in the Spectral Energy Distribution (SED), b) suppressed due to optical depth effects. If collisionally-ionized, only optical depth effects suppress lines in the X-ray spectra. In the soft X-ray regime, the optical depth effects leading to line suppression mainly come from photoelectric absorption of line photons or scattering by electrons. Section 5.2 and Section 5.3 present more detailed discussion.

The effects of continuum pumping on the optically thin line intensities, the so-called “Case C”, was introduced by Baker et al. (1938) and later discussed by Chamberlain (1953) and Ferland (1999). Their study was later extended to describe “Case D” (Luridiana et al., 2009; Peimbert et al., 2016), the optically thick counterpart of Case C. Recently, Chakraborty et al. (2021) discussed Case C and Case D in view of the future microcalorimeter missions line XRISM and Athena, focusing on line emission from H- and He-like iron.

Optical depth effects on soft X-ray spectra have been previously investigated by Storey and Hummer (1988) and Hummer and Storey (1992), who calculated the recombination line intensities of H-like carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen assuming “Case B” (Baker and Menzel, 1938) and discussed the effects of finite optical depth and dust on H-like ions. Such effects have also been observed in soft X-ray emission spectra. For instance, recent analysis of soft X-ray spectra from Reflection Grating Spectrometer (RGS) onboard XMM-Newton and High Energy Transmission Grating Spectrometer (HETGS) onboard Chandra explored several optically-thick astrophysical sources like cataclysmic variables, novae, ultraluminous X-ray sources, Seyfert galaxies, elliptical galaxies, X-ray binaries, etc (Ramsay and Cropper, 2002; Rauch et al., 2005; Okada et al., 2008; Pintore and Zampieri, 2011; de Plaa et al., 2012; Matzeu et al., 2020; Amato et al., 2021).

As previously mentioned, there have been extensive studies separately discussing the effects of continuum pumping and optical depth effects on X-ray line intensities. The current need is to develop a comprehensive theory that will account for all the atomic processes changing the soft X-ray spectra. This Chapter aims to present a

framework for interpreting the soft X-ray spectra from photoionized and collisionally-ionized plasma using the spectral synthesis code CLOUDY (Ferland et al., 2017).

We also show the application of our model on V1223 Sgr, a member of the cataclysmic variable binary star system called Intermediate Polars. We address the lack of emission from several lower atomic number H- and He-like ions, as mentioned in Islam and Mukai (2021), with an additive photoionization model and a weaker collisional component. However, our model will be applicable for any optically thick source with/without a radiation source.

5.2 Line suppression due to photoelectric and electron opacity

Photoelectric absorption of line photons or scattering by electrons can significantly suppress line intensities. Here we present CLOUDY calculations of the net emission, demonstrate line suppression due to absorption and scattering, and give simple analytical estimates of the physical processes which suppress the line emission.

CLOUDY actually determines the line emission by solving a fully coupled system of equations giving radiative transitions between levels, as originally described in Section III of Rees et al. (1989). The numerical results can be understood by considering the following approximations to the line transfer.

The fraction of photons that survives (which we call $f_{\text{modification}}$ or the “line modification factor”) after N scatterings that is subject to photoelectric absorption and electron scattering is determined by the following equation:

$$f_{\text{modification}} = (1 - P_{\text{photoelectric}} - P_{\text{scattering}})^N, \quad (5.1)$$

where N the mean number of scatterings (N) experienced by a line photon with a line-center optical depth τ before escaping an optically thick cloud (Ferland and Netzer, 1979):

$$N = \frac{1.11\tau^{1.071}}{1 + (\log\tau/5.5)^5} \quad (5.2)$$

$P_{\text{photoelectric}}$ is the probability of photoelectric absorption per scattering, and is given by the following ratio of opacities:

$$P_{\text{photoelectric}} = \frac{\kappa_{\text{photoelectric}}}{\kappa_{\text{total}}} \quad (5.3)$$

$P_{\text{scattering}}$ is the probability per scattering that a line photon will be scattered off free electrons due to the very large Doppler shift they receive and be removed from the Doppler core of the line (refer to section 7.1 in Chakraborty et al. (2020b) for a detailed discussion):

$$P_{\text{scattering}} = \frac{\kappa_{\text{scattering}}}{\kappa_{\text{total}}} \quad (5.4)$$

where the total opacity is given by

$$\kappa_{\text{total}} = \kappa_{\text{line}} + \kappa_{\text{photoelectric}} + \kappa_{\text{scattering}} \quad (5.5)$$

For the most part, $f_{\text{modification}}$ gives an estimate for the fraction of photons surviving after photoelectric absorption and electron scattering. Figure 5.1 shows photoelectric absorption opacities ($\kappa_{\text{photoelectric}}$) for temperatures between $\log T(\text{Kelvin}) = 6.2$ and $\log T(\text{Kelvin}) = 6.8$ and the scattering opacity ($\kappa_{\text{scattering}}$), assuming a thermal collisional equilibrium at T . Scattering is more important at the longer wavelengths and higher temperatures, while absorption is more important at the shorter wavelengths and lower temperatures.

Figure 5.1: Continuum opacities plotted as a function of wavelength for a cloud with $N_H=10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Red, green, yellow and blue solid lines show the absorption opacities (photoelectric) for $\log T=6.2, 6.4, 6.6,$ and $6.8,$ respectively. The black solid line shows the electron scattering opacity.

Other optical depth effects such as the Case A to B transition and Resonant Auger Destruction can suppress/amplify selected line intensities too (Chakraborty et al., 2020b,c). Numerical CLOUDY simulations on optical depth effects shown in this Chapter include all the atomic processes that can change line intensities. However, we found these effects insignificant compared to photoelectric absorption and electron scattering in the soft X-ray regime. The discussion on the optical depth effects on soft X-ray emission continues in Section 5.4 for the collisionally-ionized and photoionized cases.

Note that equation 5.1 applies in collisionally-ionized environments, where there is no external radiation source. In irradiated photoionized environments, $f_{\text{modification}}$ will also have contributions from radiative cascades prompted by absorption of line photons from the external radiation source, also known as “continuum pumping”. This is further elaborated in Section 5.3 and Section 5.4.2.

Figure 5.2: Line modification factors in C VI Ly- α , O VII He- α (w), O VIII Ly- α , and Fe XVII, in a collisionally-ionized environment, plotted as a function of column density and temperature.

5.3 Line enhancement due to continuum pumping

In photoionized systems, lines are enhanced in the presence of external radiation fields. Electrons bound to the ions absorb photons of appropriate wavelength and make transitions to higher energy states. Such transitions are usually followed by radiative cascades, which enhance the line emission associated with the participating energy levels.

Chakraborty et al. (2021) discussed the concept of continuum pumping and its effects in enhancing the line emission from H- and He-like iron. Lines can be enhanced up to ~ 30 times, and the degree of enhancement decreases with the increase in column density due to the optical depth effects, the so-called Case C to D transition. Refer to section 2 in their paper for the mathematical framework of continuum pumping and figure 1 for a simplified three level representation of Case C and Case D.

This work is an extension of the same concept for the soft X-ray regime. The observed spectra (photoionized) will have contributions from line enhancement due to continuum pumping and line suppression due to photoelectric absorption and electron scattering (further discussed in Section 5.4). Whether the lines are enhanced or suppressed depends on the interplay between these two effects. The enhancement/suppression varies with column density/optical depth, ionization parameter (ξ), and shape of the incident radiation field. For most of our calculations, we assume a

Figure 5.3: Line modification factor in OVII K- α (w), OVIII Ly- α , Ne IX K- α (w), Mg XI K- α (w), as a function of column density and ionization parameter (ξ).

power-law SED:

$$f_\nu \propto \nu^\alpha \quad (5.6)$$

with $\alpha = -1$, except for Section 5.5 where we let α to vary freely.

5.4 Optical depth effects on soft X-ray spectra

5.4.1 Collisionally ionized emission lines

The practical way to study the effect of optical depth on line intensities is to compute scaled line intensity ratios of a realistic model that includes all the optical depth effects and a simplistic model excluding optical depth effects. The line ratio stands for what fraction of line photons survive.

The realistic model includes absorption and scattering. By default, CLOUDY models include absorption but do not include scattering. The scattering was included using the command:

```
no scattering intensity
```

In the simplistic model, absorption was switched off with the command:

```
no absorption escape
```

The smaller the ratio between the realistic and simplistic model, the larger the suppression. This ratio is the numerical equivalent of $f_{\text{modification}}$, the line modification factor, studied in Section 5.2, which presented an analytical discussion on line suppression in optically thick clouds. Figure 5.2 shows this ratio for selected soft X-ray lines evaluated with CLOUDY.

Temperature and column density are physical parameters that can notably change line emission from the collisionally-ionized cloud. Thus, contour plots have been shown where temperature and column density is varied. Metallicity has been fixed at solar for simplicity. In principle, metallicity should not be taken as a free parameter, as optical depth is proportional to metallicity. This section aims to establish the framework using simplified parameters. In Section 5.5, we let metallicity vary as a free parameter along with other physical parameters to fit the observed spectrum from V1223 Sgr.

Four panels in the figure show the numerical line modification factor for C VI Ly- α ($\lambda=33.736\text{ \AA}$), OVII He- α resonance line ($\lambda=21.602\text{ \AA}$), O VIII Ly- α ($\lambda=18.969\text{ \AA}$), and Fe XVII ($\lambda=15.015\text{ \AA}$)¹ as a function of the hydrogen column density and temperature. There is significant suppression in carbon and oxygen lines and moderate suppression in the iron lines. For example, for CVI Ly- α line at the temperature of its peak emissivity, $\log T=6.2$: at $N_H=10^{23}\text{ cm}^{-2}$, the numerical line modification factor as shown in the top-left panel of the figure is ~ 0.15 . This implies, only 15 % of the CVI Ly- α line photons will make it out of the optically thick cloud at the mentioned temperature and column density².

Numerical results in the figure account for the full physics and the variation of the physical conditions across the cloud. Analytically, equation 5.1 estimates the fraction of CVI Ly- α photons surviving after photoelectric absorption and electron scattering, the only two important sources of opacity in the soft X-ray limit. At the same temperature and column density, $\tau = 3593$, $\kappa_{\text{photoelectric}} = 3.5 \times 10^{-24}\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\kappa_{\text{scattering}} = 7.9 \times 10^{-25}\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $\kappa_{\text{total}} = 1.93 \times 10^{-20}\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which implies $f_{\text{modification}} \sim 0.2$. Analytically, 20 % of the CVI Ly- α line photons will survive and make it out of the cloud.

Tables 5.1 and 5.2 list the numerical value of $f_{\text{modification}}$ at $N_H = 10^{22}\text{ cm}^{-2}$, $N_H = 10^{22.5}\text{ cm}^{-2}$, and $N_H = 10^{23}\text{ cm}^{-2}$ for $\log T = 6.4$, and 6.8 for important lines in soft X-ray spectra. $f_{\text{modification}}$ gives the fraction of line photons that will be observed by high-resolution telescopes. Note that the emission lines from the lower-Z elements exhibit maximum emissivity at the lower temperatures, where the photoelectric absorption is significant (see Figure 5.1). This will lead to a larger suppression in the lines from lower-Z elements than those of the higher-Z elements.

¹CLOUDY did not predict the Fe XVII lines in the previous versions because the default setup did not use enough levels. We changed the masterlist to use sufficient number of levels by default.

²We predict the line mean intensity $4\pi J$ averaged over all directions

Table 5.1: Modification factor ($f_{modification}$) in collisionally ionized cloud at $N_H = 10^{22}$ cm^{-2} , $N_H = 10^{22.5}$ cm^{-2} , and $N_H = 10^{23}$ cm^{-2} and $\text{Log T} = 6.4$ for important lines in soft X-ray spectra. Lines from lower atomic number elements are more suppressed than that of higher atomic number elements.

Transitions	λ (Å)	label	$f_{modification}$		
			$N_H=10^{22}$ cm^{-2}	$N_H=10^{22.5}$ cm^{-2}	$N_H=10^{23}$ cm^{-2}
C VI	33.736	Ly α	0.57	0.34	0.20
N VI	29.082	K α (x)	0.40	0.21	0.05
N VI	28.787	K α (w)	0.37	0.18	0.04
N VII	24.781	Ly α	0.83	0.69	0.24
O VII	22.101	K α (z)	0.73	0.35	0.13
O VII	21.807	K α (y)	0.71	0.33	0.12
O VII	21.804	K α (x)	0.68	0.31	0.11
O VII	21.602	K α (w)	0.61	0.24	0.08
O VIII	18.969	Ly α	0.82	0.58	0.35
Fe XVII	15.262	-	0.84	0.61	0.40
Fe XVII	15.015	-	0.86	0.62	0.46
Ne IX	13.699	K α (z)	0.99	0.97	0.65
Ne IX	13.553	K α (y)	0.99	0.95	0.61
Ne IX	13.550	K α (x)	0.96	0.87	0.53
Ne IX	13.447	K α (w)	0.81	0.64	0.33

5.4.2 Photoionized emission lines

Photoionized emission lines can be enhanced or suppressed, which is determined by the following two factors. -a) All Lyman like lines going to the ground state³ are enhanced by induced radiative excitation of the atoms/ions by continuum photons in the SED. -b) Photoelectric absorption and electron scattering in line photons can suppress the line intensities.

The line ratio to be studied here is the scaled ratio of a realistic photoionized model that includes all the optical depth effects and continuum pumping, and a simplistic model excluding optical depth effects and continuum pumping.

Section 5.4.1 listed the CLOUDY commands for switching on/off scattering and absorption processes. The continuum pumping in the simplistic model was switched off using the CLOUDY command:

`no induced processes`

This ratio between the realistic and simplistic model can be smaller or larger than 1 depending on whether the suppression due to optical thickness or the enhancement due to continuum pumping is dominating. Therefore, $f_{modification}$ can be

³Originally Baker et al. (1938) discussed the enhancement in the line emission from atomic hydrogen. Here we have studied emissions from both H- and He-like ions. All the Lyman resonance lines become significantly enhanced, forbidden lines are slightly enhanced.

Table 5.2: Modification factor ($f_{\text{modification}}$) in collisionally ionized cloud at $N_H = 10^{22}$ cm^{-2} , $N_H = 10^{22.5}$ cm^{-2} , and $N_H = 10^{23}$ cm^{-2} and $\text{Log } T = 6.8$ for important lines in soft X-ray spectra. Lines from lower atomic number elements are more suppressed.

Transitions	λ (\AA)	label	$f_{\text{modification}}$		
			$N_H=10^{22}$ cm^{-2}	$N_H=10^{22.5}$ cm^{-2}	$N_H=10^{23}$ cm^{-2}
O VIII	18.969	Ly α	0.89	0.72	0.43
Fe XVII	17.096	-	1.0	0.99	0.97
Fe XVII	17.051	-	1.0	1.0	1.0
Fe XVII	15.262	-	0.88	0.71	0.50
Fe XVII	15.015	-	0.91	0.81	0.64
Ne IX	13.699	K α (z)	0.95	0.88	0.74
Ne IX	13.553	K α (y)	0.95	0.87	0.72
Ne IX	13.550	K α (x)	0.94	0.85	0.69
Ne IX	13.447	K α (w)	0.93	0.82	0.62
Ne X	12.134	Ly α	0.95	0.86	0.69
Mg XI	9.314	K α (z)	0.99	0.97	0.92
Mg XI	9.231	K α (y)	0.99	0.96	0.90
Mg XI	9.228	K α (x)	0.97	0.93	0.84
Mg XI	9.169	K α (w)	0.95	0.85	0.71
Mg XII	8.421	Ly α	1.0	1.0	0.98
Si XIII	6.740	K α (z)	1.0	1.0	1.0
Si XIII	6.688	K α (y)	1.0	1.0	1.0
Si XIII	6.685	K α (x)	1.0	1.0	1.0
Si XIII	6.648	K α (w)	0.97	0.90	0.80
S XV	5.102	K α (z)	1.0	1.0	1.0
S XV	5.066	K α (y)	1.0	1.0	1.0
S XV	5.063	K α (x)	1.0	1.0	1.0
S XV	5.039	K α (w)	1.0	1.0	0.96

smaller or larger than 1, unlike the collisionally-ionized case, where $f_{\text{modification}}$ can only be smaller than 1.

As mentioned in Section 5.3, we assumed a power-law SED with $\alpha = -1$ for demonstration. Like the previous subsection, we adopt a solar metallicity. However, α has been considered a free parameter in Section 5.5 along with variable metallicity to fit the HETG spectrum of V1223 Sgr. Log of hydrogen column density and ionization parameter have been varied to make contour plots in Figure 5.3.

Four contour plots in the figure show the numerical modification factor for O VII He- α resonance (w) line (21.602 \AA), O VIII Ly- α (18.969 \AA), Ne IX He- α resonance (w) line (13.447 \AA), and Ne X Ly- α (12.134 \AA). The modification factor can be as large as ~ 20 (enhanced about 20 times), or as small as ~ 0.01 (suppressed about 100 times) for the OVII He- α (w) line depending on the values of N_H and ξ . The OVIII Ly- α and Ne IX He- α emission lines can be enhanced ~ 10 times, and suppressed ~ 100 times. The Ne X Ly- α line can be enhanced ~ 4 times, and suppressed \sim

Table 5.3: Modification factor ($f_{\text{modification}}$) in a photoionized cloud at $N_H = 10^{21}$ cm^{-2} , $N_H = 10^{22}$ cm^{-2} , and $N_H = 10^{23}$ cm^{-2} for $\text{Log } \xi = 1$ for important lines in soft X-ray spectra.

Transitions	λ (\AA)	label	$f_{\text{modification}}$		
			$N_H=10^{21}$ cm^{-2}	$N_H=10^{22}$ cm^{-2}	$N_H=10^{23}$ cm^{-2}
C VI	33.736	Ly α	1.05	0.38	0.03
N VI	29.082	K α (x)	1.10	0.99	0.13
N VI	28.787	K α (w)	1.75	0.72	0.07
N VII	24.781	Ly α	1.51	0.63	0.06
O VII	22.101	K α (z)	1.08	0.87	0.11
O VII	21.807	K α (y)	1.05	0.67	0.07
O VII	21.804	K α (x)	1.07	0.68	0.07
O VII	21.602	K α (w)	1.19	0.38	0.03
O VIII	18.969	Ly α	1.25	0.41	0.04
Ne IX	13.699	K α (z)	1.15	0.72	0.08
Ne IX	13.553	K α (y)	1.16	0.73	0.08
Ne IX	13.550	K α (x)	1.15	0.67	0.07
Ne IX	13.447	K α (w)	2.91	0.89	0.09
Ne X	12.134	Ly α	5.20	1.28	0.13
Mg XI	9.314	K α (z)	1.25	0.65	0.07
Mg XI	9.231	K α (y)	1.30	0.66	0.07
Mg XI	9.228	K α (x)	1.25	0.65	0.07
Mg XI	9.169	K α (w)	18.84	4.24	0.43
Mg XII	8.421	Ly α	10.96	4.69	0.50
Si XIII	6.740	K α (z)	1.39	0.56	0.05
Si XIII	6.688	K α (y)	1.49	0.60	0.06
Si XIII	6.685	K α (x)	1.37	0.55	0.05
Si XIII	6.648	K α (w)	31.60	12.11	1.21

100 times. The line modification factor for important soft X-ray lines emitted from a photoionized cloud is listed in Tables 5.3 and 5.4 for $N_H = 10^{21}$ cm^{-2} , $N_H = 10^{22}$ cm^{-2} , and $N_H = 10^{23}$ cm^{-2} for $\log \xi = 1$ and 2.5.

5.5 Application on V1223 Sgr

This section shows the application of the theory discussed in Sections 5.2, 5.3, and 5.4. We show the application on the Intermediate Polar V1223 Sgr, consisting of a white dwarf accreting material from a low mass secondary star. The matter stripped from the secondary star is magnetically channeled onto a truncated accretion disk around the white dwarf (Patterson, 1994). The X-rays from intermediate polars are generated when the infalling high-velocity (3000 - 10,000 km/s) matter encounters a shock while falling onto the white dwarf surface. The infalling particles then decelerate further in a subsonic cooling column? before hitting the surface of the white dwarf. The inner

Table 5.4: Modification factor ($f_{\text{modification}}$) in a photoionized cloud at $N_H = 10^{21}$ cm^{-2} , $N_H = 10^{22}$ cm^{-2} , and $N_H = 10^{23}$ cm^{-2} for $\text{Log } \xi = 2.5$ for important lines in soft X-ray spectra.

Transitions	λ (\AA)	label	$f_{\text{modification}}$		
			$N_H=10^{21}$ cm^{-2}	$N_H=10^{22}$ cm^{-2}	$N_H=10^{23}$ cm^{-2}
C VI	33.736	Ly α	7.27	2.43	1.27
N VI	29.082	K α (x)	0.99	0.96	0.95
N VI	28.787	K α (w)	23.74	21.32	13.37
N VII	24.781	Ly α	7.86	2.73	1.24
O VII	22.101	K α (z)	0.99	0.96	0.90
O VII	21.807	K α (y)	1.0	0.98	0.91
O VII	21.804	K α (x)	0.99	0.97	0.91
O VII	21.602	K α (w)	22.06	11.12	2.74
O VIII	18.969	Ly α	3.65	1.59	1.39
Ne IX	13.699	K α (z)	1.26	1.03	1.01
Ne IX	13.553	K α (y)	1.29	1.04	1.02
Ne IX	13.550	K α (x)	1.27	1.03	1.01
Ne IX	13.447	K α (w)	19.85	11.88	4.33
Ne X	12.134	Ly α	3.55	2.50	2.31
Mg XI	9.314	K α (z)	1.16	1.04	1.03
Mg XI	9.231	K α (y)	1.20	1.08	1.07
Mg XI	9.228	K α (x)	1.16	1.04	1.03
Mg XI	9.169	K α (w)	16.75	5.02	1.91
Mg XII	8.421	Ly α	4.88	1.87	0.95
Si XIII	6.740	K α (z)	1.10	1.08	1.07
Si XIII	6.688	K α (y)	1.16	1.15	1.14
Si XIII	6.685	K α (x)	1.09	1.08	1.06
Si XIII	6.648	K α (w)	11.83	3.54	1.38
Si XIV	6.182	Ly α	5.24	2.00	0.99

Table 5.5: Archival Chandra ACIS-S/HETG observation of V1223 Sgr.

Observation ID	Start Date/Time	Exposure(ksec)
649	2000-04-30/16:19:51	51.48

flow produces strong X-ray emission.

As displayed in Figs 5.2 and 5.3, the optical depth effects are expected to modify the important lines in the soft X-ray spectra at high column densities ($N_H \geq 10^{22.5} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). V1223 Sgr is an ideal candidate for applying our theory, as Islam and Mukai (2021) estimated that this intermediate polar has a fairly large column density ($\sim 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$). They used a combination of a cooling flow model (containing emission lines from multi-temperature collisionally-ionized plasma, and bremsstrahlung), an ionized complex absorber model, and X-ray reflection to model the summed first-order Chandra MEG spectrum of V1223 Sgr. They reported an excess flux from O VII, O VIII, Ne IX, Ne X, and Mg XI lines (see figure 3 in their paper) which could not be described with their model, and implied that these lines could have a photoionization origin.

We have also fitted the same spectrum with CLOUDY and the detailed models are described in the following paragraphs. The observational log of the spectrum is listed in Table 5.5. We obtained the first-order spectrum with the corresponding response files from the TGCat archive (Huenemoerder et al., 2011, 2013). Data processing was performed using CIAO - 4.13 (Fruscione et al., 2006) and CALDB version 4.9.4. All first-order spectra and associated responses for MEG were combined using the CIAO tool `combine_spectra`. The combined spectrum was grouped using the CIAO tool `dmgroup` with at least 30 counts per bin. This particular lower limit has been set to maintain sufficient counts for the spectral fitting while preserving the resolution of the spectra. Black data points in Figure 5.4 represent the final spectrum.

To account for the excess flux addressed in Islam and Mukai (2021), we add a photoionized model with the standard collisionally-ionized model simulated with CLOUDY. We use the CLOUDY/XSPEC interface (Porter et al., 2006) to import the model into XSPEC (Arnaud, 1996). The complete model as imported to XSPEC is: `atable(photoionized.fits) + atable(collisionally-ionized.fits)`. A chi-square statistics was used to fit the spectrum. This is a straightforward approach for fitting the spectrum while considering all the atomic processes happening in the cloud, including absorption and scattering. The collisional model has grids on temperature (equivalent to a multi-temperature approach), column density, and metallicity. The photoionized model has grids on the power-law index (α) of the SED, ionization parameter (ξ), column density, and metallicity. We tie the column density and metallicity of the collisionally-ionized and photoionized models, and let the temperature, α , ξ , and normalization of the models (N_{photo} , N_{coll}) vary freely. A solar abundance table by Asplund et al. (2009) was used for all our calculations.

Note that spectral signatures of X-ray reflection from the surface of the WD have been discussed in a number of studies (Beardmore et al., 1995; Cropper et al., 1998; Beardmore et al., 2000; Hayashi et al., 2011; Mukai et al., 2015; Hayashi et al., 2021; Islam and Mukai, 2021). X-ray reflection primarily produce two distinctive features: a compton reflection hump at $\sim 10\text{-}30 \text{ keV}$, and iron fluorescent $K\alpha$ line at 6.4 keV . As we fitted the MEG spectrum which covers the energy range $0.4 - 5.0 \text{ keV}$ ($31 - 2.5 \text{ \AA}$), we did not consider any additional model to account for the reflection. The collisional and photoionized CLOUDY models mentioned in the previous paragraph were adequate to fit the spectrum of V1223 Sgr.

Table 5.6: Best-fit parameters for a purely collisional, purely photoionized, and the complete CLOUDY model including both collisional and photoionized components fitting the summed first-order MEG spectrum of V1223 Sgr.

Parameter	Best-fit values		
	Collisional	Photoionized	Collisional + photoionized
α	-	$-0.24^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	$-0.16^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$
$\log \xi$	-	$1.635^{+0.006}_{-0.005}$	$1.632^{+0.005}_{-0.006}$
N_{photo}	-	$5.83e-11^{+1.09e-12}_{-1.62e-12}$	$6.14e-11^{+7.35e-13}_{-1.16e-12}$
Temperature (K)	$4.10e+07$	-	$1.95e+07^{+2.83e+06}_{-2.50e+06}$
Metallicity	0.35 ± 0.05	0.35 ± 0.06	0.36 ± 0.04
N_{coll}	$3.14e-10^{+2.81e-12}_{-2.79e-12}$	-	$3.63e-12^{+6.34e-13}_{-1.01e-12}$
$\log N_H$	22.05	$22.89^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	$22.91^{+0.02}_{-0.03}$
χ^2	8947.47/628	788.47/627	663.01/625

This best-fit complete CLOUDY model has been overplotted with the observed spectrum on the top-left panel of Figure 5.4. The red line represents our best-fit CLOUDY model, and the black data points represent the observed spectrum. The green line shows the component of the complete model coming from photoionization, and the blue line shows the component coming from collisional ionization. We get a significantly better fit for O VII, O VIII, Ne IX, Ne X, and Mg XI lines than shown on Islam and Mukai (2021). We find that, O VII, O VIII, Ne IX, Ne X, Mg XI, Si XIII line emission mostly comes from photoionization, although collisional ionization contributes to the formation of Ne X, Al XIII, Si XIV, and Ar XVII lines. The continuum is dominated by the photoionized component.

The solid red line on the top-right and bottom-left panels show the fit to the same spectrum for a pure collisionally-ionized and a pure photoionized model. The pure collisionally-ionized model produces a significantly poor fit to the spectrum. The pure photoionized model produces a poor fit to the spectrum in the lower wavelength region with missing Al XIII and Si XIV lines. The bottom-right panel of the figure shows the consequence of switching off the optical depth effects and continuum pumping. The red line is the CLOUDY model with the above-mentioned processes switched off. The fit is considerably worse than our complete CLOUDY model which includes these atomic processes, especially the fit to the continuum and emission lines from O VII, O VIII, Ne IX, Ne X, Mg XI, and Si XIV. This shows the importance of taking into account the effects of optical depth and continuum excitation.

Table 5.6 lists the best-fit CLOUDY model parameters for our complete model (collisionally-ionized + photoionized) as well as pure collisionally-ionized and photoionized models. The errors are reported at a 90% confidence interval. The χ^2 for the pure collisionally-ionized model is 8947.47 for 628 dof; errors in temperature and column density could not be constrained. The χ^2 for the pure photoionized model is 788.47 for 627 dof, and our complete model is 663.01 for 625 dof.

Figure 5.4: On all four panels, black data points show the Chandra High Energy Transmission Grating MEG combined first-order spectrum. a) The solid red line shows our best-fit CLOUDY model. Green and blue lines show the photoionized and collisionally-ionized components of the best-fit model separately. b) The solid red line shows the CLOUDY model fitting the observed spectrum considering a purely collisionally-ionized environment. c) The solid red line shows the CLOUDY model fitting the observed spectrum considering a purely photoionized environment. d) The solid red line shows our best-fit CLOUDY model without considering the optical depth and continuum pumping effects discussed in Sections 5.2, 5.3, and 5.4.

5.6 Summary

- The effects of optical depth have been discussed on soft X-ray emission lines. A cloud can be collisionally-ionized or photoionized. For a collisionally-ionized cloud, the atomic physical processes that contribute to the suppression in soft X-ray lines are photoelectric absorption of line photons and electron scattering. Photoelectric absorption is temperature dependent, electron scattering is not. The temperature dependence of photoelectric absorption opacity is shown on Figure 5.1. The line modification factor ($f_{\text{modification}}$) quantifies the fraction of photons surviving the absorption and scattering (see equation 5.1). Figure 5.2

shows the numerical equivalent of $f_{\text{modification}}$ as a function of hydrogen column density and temperature for C VI Ly- α , O VII He- α (w), O VIII Ly- α , and Fe XVII lines. Tables 5.1 and 5.2 list $f_{\text{modification}}$ for important soft X-ray lines at $N_H = 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $N_H = 10^{22.5} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, and $N_H = 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $\log T = 6.4$ and 6.8.

For a collisionally-ionized cloud, $0 \leq f_{\text{modification}} \leq 1$. As shown in the tables, $f_{\text{modification}}$ is smaller for lower- Z elements like carbon, oxygen, and neon, but approaches 1 for higher- Z elements like magnesium, silicon, and sulfur. This implies that soft X-ray line intensities for the lower- Z elements can be significantly suppressed.

- For the photoionized cloud, lines can be enhanced or suppressed. Continuum pumping can strengthen the Lyman lines in H- and He-like ions. Absorption and scattering can suppress the lines. Whether a line will be suppressed or enhanced is jointly determined by these two factors. Unlike the collisionally-ionized cloud, $f_{\text{modification}}$ can be greater or smaller than 1. Figure 5.3 shows the numerical equivalent of $f_{\text{modification}}$ as a function of hydrogen column density and ionization parameter for an $\alpha=-1$ power-law SED for O VII He- α (w), O VIII Ly- α , Ne IX He- α (w), and Ne X Ly- α . Tables 5.3 and 5.4 show $f_{\text{modification}}$ for important soft X-ray photoionized lines for $N_H = 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $N_H = 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, and $N_H = 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for $\log \xi = 1$, and 2.5.
- A hybrid of collisional ionization and photoionization is also observed in many astronomical sources. One such example is illustrated in Section 5.5. We modeled the MEG spectrum from V1223 Sgr, an intermediate polar, using the CLOUDY/XSPEC interface. This is the first application of this interface after the recent CLOUDY developments for meeting the spectroscopic standards of the future microcalorimeter missions.

We used a combination of CLOUDY-simulated collisionally-ionized and photoionized models to fit the spectrum. We found that the photoionized component dominates the shape of the continuum. Emissions from O VII, O VIII, Ne IX, Ne X, Mg XI, and Si XIII lines originate in the photoionized plasma. Al XIII, Si XIV, and Ar XVII lines originate in the collisionally-ionized plasma. Islam and Mukai (2021) fitted the same spectrum of V1223 Sgr and reported excess emission from O VII, O VIII, Ne IX, Ne X, and Mg XI lines which couldn't be described with their absorbed cooling flow model. We fit these lines simply by adding a photoionized component to the standard collisional component. Table 5.6 lists the best-fit parameters from our best-fit CLOUDY model, and top-left panel of Figure 5.4 shows the best-fit CLOUDY model overplotted with the observed spectrum.

On the contrary, the observed spectrum was ill-fitted using pure collisionally-ionized and pure photoionized CLOUDY models, as shown in the top-right and bottom-left panels of Figure 5.4. We also show the consequences of switching off atomic physical processes like optical depth effects and continuum pumping

in the bottom-right panel of the figure. The solid red line shows the fit after switching off the atomic physical processes. The fit is considerably worse than our best-fit model shown on the top-left panel, including all atomic processes. This shows the importance of incorporating optical depth effects and continuum pumping in the spectral simulation codes.

Chapter 6 Improvements on energies for $K\alpha$ transitions

6.1 Introduction

CLOUDY (Ferland et al., 2017) has long predicted intensities of X-ray lines due to its need to do physical simulations of a non-equilibrium plasma. The original design for one and two-electron species took advantage of scaling relationships along iso-electronic sequences. A series of papers, part of Ryan Porter’s thesis, reporting on this development include Porter et al. (2005) and Porter et al. (2012) on optical emission from He I and Porter and Ferland (2007) on X-ray emission from O VII. While the physics remains close to the state of the art, the level energies and line wavelengths derived in the older work had largely sufficient accuracy for the then-operational optical observatories and X-ray missions but not for the upcoming missions.

The available spectroscopic resolution has increased dramatically with the advent of microcalorimeter missions like Hitomi and the upcoming missions *XRISM* and *Athena*. Atomic processes are very sensitive to line wavelengths due to line overlap with nearby satellites (Mehdipour et al., 2015; Chakraborty et al., 2020b) and require precise energies. This development is a work in progress and will be part of a future release of CLOUDY. In the meantime, we have improved the treatment of levels and line energies in the release version of CLOUDY, as described below. These improvements will be part of the upcoming C17.03 release.

6.2 Results

The previous versions of CLOUDY, through to C17.02, used ionization potentials (I_{ion}) derived by Verner et al. (1996) with four significant digits. Level energies were then derived from the following equation:

$$I_n = I_{\text{ion}}/n^2 \quad (6.1)$$

and the $K\alpha$ energies were calculated from:

$$E_{K\alpha}^{\text{old}} = I_1 - I_2 \quad (6.2)$$

The I_{ion} ’s in equation 6.1, stored in the ‘phfit.dat’ file in the CLOUDY data directory, were used to compute the photoionization cross-sections in Verner et al. (1996). Although these values are reasonably accurate, microcalorimeter observations require much better precision. We update the ionization potentials in ‘phfit.dat’ for H-like ions with those of NIST (Kramida et al., 2018), keeping up to the eighth significant digits. Our updated version of ‘phfit.dat’ will be included in the C17.03 release.

Following this, we generated a fourth-order polynomial for the energy correction (ΔE) for better agreement with the NIST $K\alpha$ energies:

$$\Delta E = 0.1783Z^4 - 1.8313Z^3 + 27.803Z^2 - 208.04Z + 570.59 \quad (6.3)$$

The updated energies ($E_{K\alpha}^{\text{new}}$) for the $K\alpha$ transitions are given by the following equation:

$$E_{K\alpha}^{\text{new}} = E_{K\alpha}^{\text{old}} + \Delta E \quad (6.4)$$

Figure 6.1: The absolute value of the difference between NIST and CLOUDY $K\alpha$ energies versus $K\alpha$ energies for H-like ions of elements between $6 \leq Z \leq 30$. The x-axis on top shows the corresponding atomic numbers (Z). Red triangles show the difference between energies in the updated version of CLOUDY (C17.03) and NIST. Green circles show the energy difference between the previous versions of CLOUDY (from ~ 2005 to C17.02) and NIST. The solid, dashed, and dotted lines indicate the absolute values of the energy accuracy of the current and future X-ray observatories. Refer to the results section for a detailed description.

Figure 6.1 shows the absolute values of the differences in $K\alpha$ energies between NIST and CLOUDY for H-like ions versus $K\alpha$ energies for elements between $6 \leq Z \leq 30$. The red triangles and green circles show the difference with NIST for the updated CLOUDY (C17.03) energies and the old CLOUDY energies appearing in C17.02 and before, respectively. The figure also shows the absolute values of the energy accuracy

of current and future X-ray observatories. The solid and dashed magenta lines represent the energy accuracy of *Chandra* HEG and MEG, respectively¹. The solid and dotted brown lines indicate the accuracy of RGS1 (1st and 2nd order) and RGS2 (1st and 2nd order) onboard XMM-Newton². The solid black and blue lines represent the energy accuracy of *XRISM* (Ishisaki et al., 2018) and *Athena* (Barret et al., 2016), respectively. The updated $K\alpha$ energies in the revised CLOUDY release (C17.03) are ~ 15 -4000 times more precise than that of C17.02. This energy precision is also much superior to the energy accuracy of the current and future X-ray instruments. The improved CLOUDY energies will therefore be in excellent agreement with the future microcalorimeter observations.

Finally, we created a patch file: ‘H_total_correction.diff’, which includes the changes leading up to the updated $K\alpha$ energies ($E_{K\alpha}^{\text{new}}$). These changes will be part of C17.03, and are now posted to the CLOUDY user group³. Updates on the development of CLOUDY are posted to its wiki⁴.

The improvement described here is made only for the $K\alpha$ energies for elements between Carbon ($Z=6$) and Zinc ($Z=30$) since it is negligible for lighter elements. The doublet splitting for the 2p levels is not included in this update but is part of the thesis work and will be incorporated into the next major release of CLOUDY. This future version will read extensive data files from NIST instead of using the above correction.

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¹<https://cxc.harvard.edu/proposer/POG/html/chap8.html>

²https://xmm-tools.cosmos.esa.int/external/xmm_user_support/documentation/uhb/rgs.html

³<https://cloudyastrophysics.groups.io/g/Main/topics>

⁴<https://trac.nublado.org/wiki/NewC17>

Chapter 7 Conclusions

In my PhD thesis, I developed tools, spectral diagnostic methods, and explained various atomic physical phenomena to interpret high-resolution spectra which will be observed by future microcalorimeter missions like *XRISM* and *Athena*. This work involved simulating high-resolution X-ray spectra with the spectral synthesis code CLOUDY and comparing the simulation with the observed spectra by the *Hitomi* satellite.

I developed CLOUDY to meet the spectroscopic challenges of the future microcalorimeter missions. These developments include incorporating precise energies for $K\alpha$ transitions for elements between Carbon and Zinc, updating the electron collision strengths, and adding electron scattering effects for larger column densities.

I discussed the importance of Fe^{23+} in determining the line intensities of the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex in an optically thick cloud, and investigated Resonant Auger Destruction (RAD) with CLOUDY. Although initially motivated by the Perseus cluster, these calculations are extended to the wide range of column densities encountered in astronomy. A Fe XXV line photon can change/lose its identity upon absorption by three-electron iron as a result of “line interlocking.” This may lead to the autoionization of the absorbing ion, ultimately destroying the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ photon by RAD. Out of the four members in the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ complex, a significant fraction of the x line photons are absorbed by Fe^{23+} and destroyed, causing the x line intensity to decrease. For example, at a hydrogen column density of 10^{25} cm^{-2} , 32% of x photons are destroyed due to RAD while w is mostly unaffected. The line intensity of y is slightly (2%) reduced. z is not directly affected by RAD, but the contrasting behavior between z and x line intensities points toward the possible conversion of a tiny fraction (2%) of x photons into z photons. The change in line intensities due to electron scattering escape off fast thermal electrons is also discussed.

I also presented a novel column density diagnostic from optically thin (Case A) to optically thick (Case B) transition in H- and He-like iron. The Fe XXV $K\alpha$ line ratios computed with CLOUDY was compared with the *Hitomi* observations in the outer region of the Perseus to measure/constrain the column density. The effect of turbulence on the Fe XXV $K\alpha$ line ratios and interplay between column density and metallicity was also discussed.

I established four asymptotic limits- Case A, Case B, Case C, and Case D to describe different line formation processes in H- and He-like systems for astronomical sources emitting in the X-rays. Case A occurs when the Lyman line optical depths are very small and photo-excitation does not occur. Line photons escape the cloud without any scattering. Case B occurs when the Lyman line optical depths are large enough for photons to undergo multiple scatterings. Case C occurs when a broadband continuum source strikes an optically thin cloud. The Lyman lines are enhanced by induced radiative excitation of the atoms/ions by continuum photons, also known as continuum pumping. A fourth, less studied scenario, where the Case B spectrum is enhanced by continuum pumping, is called Case D. Here, I estab-

lished the mathematical foundation of Cases A, B, C, and D in an irradiated cloud with CLOUDY. I also showed the total X-ray emission spectrum for all four cases within the energy range 0.1-10 keV at the resolving power of *XRISM* around 6 keV. Additionally, I showed that the combined effect of electron scattering and partial blockage of continuum pumping reduces the resonance line intensities. Such reduction increases with column density and can serve as an important tool to measure the column density/optical depth of the cloud.

I further extended this analysis done for H- and He-like iron to the soft X-rays. For the collisionally ionized cloud, the atomic physical processes that contribute to the suppression in soft X-ray lines are photoelectric absorption of line photons and electron scattering. For the photoionized cloud, lines can be enhanced or suppressed, which is jointly determined by absorption/scattering and continuum pumping. I also showed the application of this theory on V1223 Sgr, a class of cataclysmic variable binary star system called Intermediate Polar.

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